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Hygroscopic Absorption to Falling Films:
The Effects of the Concentration Level

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in Engineering" in Tel - Aviv University.

by

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This work is dedicated
to

Prof. Michael (Micha) Bentwich

A Scientist, Idealist, Teacher
and Friend

Who died prematurely on
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1. Abstract

Absorption of vapor into chemical solutions, particularly brines is characterized by a high concentration level of the absorbate. Almost all the theoretical investigations which were conducted until now have neglected the influence of the absorbate concentration level on the mass transfer rate. The aim of this work is to investigate analytically the influence of the absorbate concentration level in liquid film on the absorption process.

This theoretical research is an extension of Higbie's theory [H3] for isothermal absorption and also an extension of Grossman's work [G3] for non isothermal absorption, which is based on low concentration and short contact time.

The analysis is carried out in two stages: first, a model for isothermal absorption is presented and second, a model for non isothermal absorption developed, which takes into account simultaneous heat and mass transfer. The main assumptions incorporated in the model are: 1) short exposure time, 2) uniform film thickness, 3) constant physical properties.

The governing diffusion equation is nonlinear in the absorbate concentration, which differs from the low concentration case, where the equation can be approximated by a linear equation. An analytical solution for the governing equation was established during the investigation. In the case of isothermal absorption it leads to a set of two algebraic equations, and in the case of non isothermal absorption it leads to a set of four algebraic equations. The solution in both cases was carried out numerically by a computer.

One of the principal conclusions is that theories which are based on the assumption of low concentration can lead to incorrect estimation of the mass transfer rate. Moreover, it has been found that mass transfer rate increases with the concentration level. The meaning of this result is that boundary layer growth is faster in high concentration film compare to a film with lower concentration.

The coupling between the heat transfer and the mass transfer in non isothermal absorption (where the absorption process is accompanied by heat release) causes a decrease of the mass transfer rate, which is caused by the sensitivity of the interfacial equilibrium concentration to the free interface temperature. The parameter $\Lambda / \sqrt{Le}$ expresses the amount of coupling between the absorption phenomenon and the heat transfer. As the parameter increases the coupling between the absorption and the heat transfer is stronger. The heat transfer as well the mass transfer are augmented relative to infinite dilution solution (note that even though Nusselt numbers remain the same the augmentation of the heat flux is due to higher driving force).

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5. Nomenclature

b, d	- constants which depend on the materials and the pressure equation (3.10)
C	- solution molar density, [mole/m ³]
C_A	- absorbate concentration, [moles/m ³]
C_0	- initial concentration or entrance concentration, [moles/m ³]
C_p	- specific heat of liquid [kJ/kg-°C]
C^*	- equilibrium concentration at given temperature and pressure, [$\frac{\text{moles}}{\text{m}^2}$]
D_{AB}	- diffusion coefficient of species A in B, [m ² /sec]
E	- $\frac{(C_0 - C^*)}{C}$
g	- the gravity acceleration, [m/sec ²]
$\bar{h}$	- the average film height, [m]
H_a	- heat of absorption [kJ/kmol]
k	- thermal conductivity of liquid [kW/m-°C]
N_{Ax_1}	- molar flux of specie A in x_1 direction, [moles/sec-m ²]
N_{Ay_1}	- molar flux of specie A in y_1 direction, [moles/sec-m ²]
N_{Bx_1}	- molar flux of specie B in x_1 direction, [moles/sec-m ²]
N_{By_1}	- molar flux of specie B in y_1 direction, [moles/sec-m ²]
p	- the local pressure, [Pa]
P_v	- pressure which exist at the interface [Pa]
$\bar{u}$	- average film velocity, [m/sec]
U	- velocity in flow direction, [m/sec]
$U(y_1)$	- velocity in x_1 direction as function as y_1 , [m/sec]
U_{max}	- interfacial velocity, [m/sec]
v	- velocity along y_1 coordinate, [m/sec]
W	- film wideness (perpendicular to x_1 and y_1), [m]

- X - molar fraction of the absorbate
X_A - molar fraction of absorbate, $X_A = \frac{C_A}{C}$
X* - equilibrium mole fraction at the liquid interface
x₁ - coordinate downstream [m]
y₁ - perpendicular coordinate to the flow direction, [m]

Greek Symbols

- Γ - liquid flow rate, [kg/sec-m]
α - liquid thermal diffusivity, [m²/sec]
δ - The film thickness, [m]
θ - the surface inclination angle
μ - viscosity, [Kg/m-sec]
ν - kinematic viscosity, [m²/m]
ρ - specific density, [Kg/m³]
σ - surface tension, [N/m]
τ_o - shearing stress at the interface, [Pa]

Dimensionless group

- Fr - $\frac{u}{\sqrt{gh}}$
Fi - equation (1.3)
Le - Lewis number, D_{AB}/α , Pe_T/Pe_m
Re - Reynolds number, $\frac{4\Gamma}{\mu}$
Sc - Schmidt number, $\frac{D_{AB}\rho}{\mu}$
Pe_m - $\frac{\delta U_{max}}{D_{AB}}$
Pe_T - $\frac{\delta U_{max}}{\alpha}$
x - normalized coordinate downstream
y - normalized perpendicular coordinate to the flow direction
Ξ - ratio $\frac{X_A}{X^*}$

$$\Phi - \frac{C_A - C_0}{C_e - C_0}$$

$$\Theta - \frac{T^* - T_0}{T_e - T_0}$$

$$\Lambda - \text{normalized heat of condensation-absorption, } \frac{LeH_a (C_e - C_0)}{\rho C_p (T_e - T_0)}$$

$$\Omega - \frac{Sh}{Sh^0}$$

η - dimensionless absorbate molar flux

Subscripts

A - absorbate

B - non-volatile absorbent

v - condensing vapor

0 - at inlet

e - at equilibrium without change in the other property

max - maximum

Superscripts

* - at equilibrium

- - average

0 - infinite dilution

6. Introduction

Absorption of gases into liquid film appears in many processes in chemical and mechanical engineering technology. The areas in which this process appears are heat exchanger with or without direct mass contact, processes involved in chemical reactors, separation of gases from a liquid in distillation process, power cycle based on the absorption and condensation [M2]. Recently there is a special interest in absorption on concentrated salt solutions, due to the potential in heat recovery to produce energy. There are several known geometries for these processes, yet the geometry of absorption in liquid film is particularly interesting. Absorption in films enables the achievement of high heat and mass transfer rates with simultaneous heat transfer to an adjacent media (through the wall) in contrast to absorption process in sprays and packed columns which are usually adiabatic. This possibility of achieving high transfer rate, additionally to the possibility in changing the film geometry, increases the designer flexibility to control and to govern the process.

Generally in gas-liquid system the absorption process is accompanied by heat transfer. There is a coupling between the heat transfer and mass transfer due to the following reasons:

- a) the material transfer by diffusion carry energy with it,
- b) the change in the concentration or temperature due to the heat and or mass transfer changes the physical properties of the liquid,
- c) absorption process is associated with release of the vapor latent heat and mixing heat which heat the film,

d) the influence of the boundary conditions, equilibrium condition at the interface, depend on the temperature and concentration.

There might be more reasons to this coupling like chemical reaction etc.

Beside the coupling between the heat and mass transfer, almost all the absorption processes occur when the absorbate concentration level in the liquid is finite not necessarily low. The power cycle based on absorption [M2] as well the distillation are examples to processes in which the absorbate concentration is relatively high. It needs to mention that mass transfer in high concentration differs from mass transfer in low concentration. Not only the physical properties are unlike but also the inherent character of governing equation is different.

Simultaneous heat and mass transfer is not easy to mathematical analysis even though there are some theoretical studies on the subject, see for example Grossman [G1] who assumed low concentration of absorbate. The influence of the concentration level on the isothermal absorption can be seen from the Arnold's work [A3] that deals with isothermal absorption assuming a constant molar flux in an infinite stagnate medium. At this stage there is no theoretical research on in system of high absorbate concentration level.

The work object is to build a model in which the heat and mass transfer occurs at high absorbate concentration level in the liquid film. This model could be in the future a base to more sophisticated models in different geometries.

1. Literature review

1.1 General

This literature review deals with the physical phenomena which are associated with the gas absorption process into an inclined liquid film surface. The first part of the review deals with the fluid mechanics of the film, the second part deals with mass transfer, and the third part deals with simultaneous mass and heat transfer phenomenon. Due to the analytical character of this work the literature search is concentrated on theoretical works.

Exhibit 1.1 General description of thin liquid film

1.2 The hydrodynamics of thin film

In this part a general description of the thin film hydrodynamics is given, and mathematical models are discussed. This extension of the

1.2 The hydrodynamics of thin film

In this part a general description of the thin film hydrodynamics is given, and mathematical models are discussed. This extension of the literature review shows in which areas the model can be applied and in where it is inadequate.

Thin film flow is a liquid flow of thin thickness compared to other dimensions of the system. This flow is characterized by free interface of a liquid which is in contact with the gaseous phase (air or vapor), therefore one can consider this flow as two phase flow. Here, the flow will be treated as one phase flow with free interface. See the general description of the flow in Exhibit 1.1.

1.2.1 Thin film classification

Almost all the researchers agree that there are several patterns in this kind of flow. It is harder to define the transition boundaries between the various flow patterns, because it is depended on the researchers subjective distinction. Wide literature reviews up to 1964 have been done by Fulford [F1] and later by Rosenberg [R1]. The subjective distinction of the flow pattern leads to different definitions. Theoretically, there are many factors that affect the flow which can be expressed by dimensionless numbers (e.g. Reynolds number, Froude number and Weber number) as well other factors like the properties of surface on which the fluid flows. A typical approach is to attribute the flow patterns to Re number, which is defined according to the following equation:

$$Re = \frac{4\Gamma}{\mu} = \frac{4\bar{u}h}{\nu} \quad (1.1)$$

Where -

Γ - mass flow rate per unit width

μ - viscosity

ν - kinematic viscosity

$\bar{u}, h$ - the average film velocity and the height, respectively

A large number of researchers divided the flow patterns into three main categories. The criteria to classification that have been proposed by the different researchers are summarized in Table 1.

1. laminar flow - the film thickness in this flow pattern is uniform and the velocity profile is parabolic
2. wavy laminar flow - due to instabilities in the free interface, waves are created (Chien [C3]). The flow field is partially laminar and partially turbulent, with turbulence increasing with Reynolds number.
3. turbulent flow - the whole flow field is turbulent. In addition, the flow surface is in "chaos".

source		laminar flow	wavy laminar flow	turbulent flow
Levich	[L3]	Re<20:30	20:30<Re<1500	1500<Re
Bird	[B6]	Re<20:50	20:50<Re<1500	1500<Re
Dukler	[D2]	Re<1080	-	1080
Cooper	[C5]	Re<2100	-	2100<Re
Friedman	[F2]	Re<20:30	20:30<Re<1500	1500<Re
Stirba	[S2]	-	-	2000<Re
Kirkbride	[K4]	Re<8	Re>8	-

Table 1 flow regime classification

The difference between the various researchers leads to the conclusion that classification based on Re alone is not sufficient. A different approach is presented in Chow's book [C4]. The author mentions five different regimes, and the distinguished boundaries between various patterns is based on Re and Fr numbers together. When Fr number is defined in the following way:

$$Fr = \frac{\bar{u}}{\sqrt{gh}} \quad (1.2)$$

Where -

- $\bar{u}$ - the average film velocity
- g - the gravity acceleration
- $\bar{h}$ - the average film height

The regimes that have been suggested by Chow are:

- 1) laminar flow subcritical, $Fr < 1$ and Re in the laminar range,

- 2) laminar flow supercritical, $Fr > 1$ and Re in the laminar range,
- 3) transient kind of flow $500 < Re < 2000$,
- 4) turbulent flow subcritical $Fr < 1$ and Re in the turbulent range,
- 5) turbulent flow supercritical $Fr > 1$ and Re in the turbulent range.

A somewhat different approach is proposed by Ishigai et al [11] based on film number which is defined as the following:

$$Fi = \frac{\sigma^3 g^2}{\rho^3 \nu^4} \quad (1.3)$$

Where -

- σ - surface tension
- ν - kinematic viscosity
- ρ - specific density

Also, according to this approach there are five regimes

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--|
| 1. laminar flow | $1.88 \times Fi^{0.1} < Re,$ |
| 2. the first transition area | $1.88 \times Fi^{0.1} < Re < 8.8 \times Fi^{0.1},$ |
| 3. stable wavy flow | $8.8 \times Fi^{0.1} < Re < 300,$ |
| 4. the second transition area | $300 < Re < 1600,$ |
| 5. full turbulent flow | $1600 < Re.$ |

More remarks on the classification of the flow

- 1) A liquid film is characterized by the existence of an entrance zone, where waves are created, and a developed flow zone. The entrance length is characterized by smooth laminar flow. The entrance length is not constant and depends on several parameters. Examining the wave inception distance shows that the wave inception line move farther away downstream with increase of Re number. Therefore, it should be emphasized that all the discussions later on deal with developed zone.
- 2) Existence of minimum wettability flow rate - as it is observed from experiments, when the flow rate reduces it comes to a point of a critical Re number for which there is no more continuous flow and the film breaks up and/or streams in a several currents.

More general discussions are given in Rosenberg [R1], Moalem et al [M3].

1.2.2 Smooth laminar flow

One of the first researchers who solved analytically the momentum equation for developed smooth laminar film flow was Nusselt [N3]. Neglecting the inertia terms, shearing stresses at the interface, pressure loss in the flow direction and velocity differences in the flow direction, the following equation has been established:

$$v \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y_1^2} = - g \sin \theta \quad (1.4)$$

Where -

- U - velocity in flow direction
- y_1 - perpendicular coordinate to the flow direction
- θ - the surface inclination angle

Assuming no slip condition at the rigid surface and no shear stress at the free interface, the boundary conditions have the following form:

$$U(y_1=0) = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial y_1}(y_1=h) = 0 \quad (1.6)$$

The velocity profile which obtained by solving equation (1.4) with boundary conditions (1.5) and (1.6) is.

$$U = \frac{g \sin \theta}{2\nu} (2h - y_1^2). \quad (1.7)$$

By integration along y_1 axis of the velocity profile and comparing with the feed flow rate per width, the following relationship is obtained:

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{2\nu\Gamma}{g \sin \theta}} \quad (1.8)$$

Nusselt's derivations are in good agreement with experimental results at low Re numbers. Similar derivations can be found in Fallach et al [F1]. Further developments that take into account other parameters have been carried out by other researchers, for example Fulford [F3] presented a solution to equation (1.4) with shearing stress at the free surface:

$$U = \frac{g \sin \theta}{2\nu} (2h - y^2) - \frac{\tau_0}{\mu} y \quad (1.9)$$

Where -

τ_0 - shearing stress at the interface

The same researcher [F3] accounted also for the pressure loss. Solutions considering the fluid inertia and pressure loss can be found (Nedderman [N2] and also Golan and Sideman [G1]). They assume parabolic velocity profile and use the following momentum equation:

$$U \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_1} + \nu \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial y_1} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_1^2} + g \sin \theta \quad (1.10)$$

Where -

p - the local pressure

v - the velocity along y_1 coordinate

After performing integration on the film thickness and assuming parabolic velocity profile a differential equation is obtained. This equation can be solved numerically with known initial conditions. This model uses the assumption of parabolic velocity which was checked later on by experimental work like Wilkes [W1] and found to be reasonable for low Re numbers.

1.2.3 Laminar Wavy flow

A substantial work has been performed on wave formation in laminar films. For low Re numbers the flow is mostly laminar and the velocity profile is parabolic with slight changes at the interface. Kapitza [K1] was one of the first who looked into the problem analytically. He wrote and solve the momentum equation in the flow direction considering the surface tension forces. He assumed that solution has an harmonic form and the waves are long compare to film thickness. He neglected the term $v\partial U/\partial y_1$ in the two dimensional momentum equations. This omission has been corrected by Levich [L3] and it has been found that it does not have significant effects on the solution. By using a energy balance Kapitza [K1] showed that the film "will try" to get an average thickness which has minimum energy for a given flow rate. According to this calculation there is a Re number below which the flow is stable and for water it is about 23.2. Binnie [B17], Hanratty and Hershman [H1] and Benjamin [B2] discuss extensively this topic.

Massot et al [M1] solve the two momentum equations for x and y directions and found that the average wave velocity depended on We number. When $We \rightarrow 0$ $c = 3$ (c is the ratio between the wave velocity and

the film average velocity) and when $We \rightarrow \infty$ $c = 1.5$. These results are in agreement with experiments at low Re numbers.

In all these approaches the conditions for the existence of a simple harmonic solution (sinuous waves) are looked for. Therefore, they describe the flow for very low Reynolds numbers and in the waves inception area [B13]. In the developed flow area the waves are not sinusoidal and have very large amplitude, at least of the order of the film thickness. The waves carry most of the liquid mass and move on a very long thin substrate film. An hydrodynamic model which describe the different parameters of these waves was recently developed by Brauner [B11], Brauner et al [B10] and Moalem et al [M2]. These reports extend to collaborate the effects of concurrent gas flow Brauner et al [B14] and to countercurrent flow of gas in the flooding zone, Brauner et al [B12].

1.2.4 Turbulent flow

The principal approach in dealing with turbulent film flow has been mainly experimental. Recently, there are some mathematical models which attempt to describe the phenomenon. Among the first works is Dukler and Bergelin [D2]. They used the universal profile of Nikuradze, while using the non dimensional velocity and non dimensional distance and got a relationship between the flow rate and the film thickness. This work does not collaborate in it the wavy nature of the free-surface.

Other works suggested correlations between Reynolds number and the film thickness based on Nusselt's calculation. An example of this kind equation is Brotz correlation (1954).

$$h_N = 0.0682 \times \text{Re}^{2/3} \quad (1.11)$$

Later works in this area differ in the velocity profile nature assumed in attempt to describe the turbulent velocity field close to the plate surface and to the free interface. It turns out that there are no significant differences between all these relations. Further literature review can be found in Grossman [G5], Mudawwer [M4], Dukler [D2], Yih [Y2], Zfati [Z1], and another extended survey can be found in Itzhak [I2].

1.3 Mass transfer

1.3.1 Introduction - development of the basic equation (steady state)

The mass balance for element absorbate A described in Exhibit 1.2.

$$N_{Ay_1} W \Delta x_1|_{y_1} + N_{Ax_1} W \Delta y_1|_{x_1} - N_{Ay_1} W \Delta x_1|_{y_1 + \Delta y_1} - N_{Ax_1} W \Delta y_1|_{x_1 + \Delta x_1} = 0 \quad (1.12)$$

Assuming there are no chemical reactions.

Where -

N_{Ax_1} - molar flux of species A in x_1 direction, moles/sec-m²

N_{Ay_1} - molar flux of species A in y_1 direction, moles/sec-m²

W - film wideness (perpendicular to x_1 and y_1)

Dividing equation (1.12) by $W \Delta y_1 \Delta x_1$ and performing the usual limiting process as the volume element becomes infinitesimally small, we get

$$\frac{\partial N_{Ax_1}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial N_{Ay_1}}{\partial y_1} = 0. \quad (1.13)$$

Utilizing the molar flux equation in x direction for Pe_m large enough (Rotem et al [R2] showed that it possible to neglect the diffusion flux in the flow direction) the molar flux equation has the following form: (relative to stationary coordinates)

Exhibit 1.2 Mass balance on an element

$$N_{Ax_1} = -D_{AB} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} + X_A (N_{Ax_1} + N_{Bx_1}) = C_A U(y_1) \quad (1.14)$$

Where -

- C_A - absorbate concentration, moles/m³
- D_{AB} - diffusion coefficient of species A in B, m²/sec
- $U(y_1)$ - velocity in x_1 direction as function as y_1 , m/sec
- X_A, X - molar fraction of absorbate, $X_A = C_A/C$

- C - solution molar density, mole/m³
N_{Bx₁} - molar flux of species B in x₁ direction, moles/sec-m²

Using the molar flux equation for the y₁ direction:

$$N_{Ay_1} = -D_{AB} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} + X_A (N_{Ay_1} + N_{By_1}) \quad (1.15)$$

Where -

- N_{By₁} - molar flux of species B in y₁ direction, moles/sec-m²

The term N_{By₁} vanishes because the specie B (absorbent) does not penetrates neither the free interface nor the solid wall (for example, for brine water the material B is salt). Therefore equation (1.15) will have the following form:

$$N_{Ay_1} = -\frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X_A)} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} \quad (1.16)$$

Substituting equation (1.14) and equation (1.16) into equation (1.13) and for small X_A (compare to 1) the following expression is obtained:

$$U(y_1) \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial x_1} = D_{AB} \frac{\partial^2 C_A}{\partial y_1^2} \quad (1.17)$$

Almost all the studies up to now (except Arnold's work [A3], see section 1.3.2.1) neglect the term X_A and actually did not arrive at equation (1.16).

In similar fashion the heat equation can be derived.

1.3.2 Analytical solution for heat or mass transfer

The similarity between the heat transfer and the mass transfer leads many researchers to conclusion that the mathematical solutions is the same, but the physical constant will be different. Therefore, a

common frame is used for treating solutions for the mass and heat transfer problems.

1.3.2.1 Short time contact theory (Penetration theory)

Mass transfer in a variety of physical system (e.g. electrochemistry and corrosion, see Hershey [H2]) may occur in very limited zones, sometime at the interface vicinity between the liquid to the gas, therefore, analysis for short contact time has been employed. (Short contact time is often called low penetration theory.) This analysis is sometimes practical and sometime gives only directions and estimations on the processes. Moreover, there are researchers who use these analytical solutions in numerical derivations (for example, Grossman [G3]). The first that developed the topic of "short contact time" was carried by Higbie [H3] (See more comprehensive derivations in chapter 2). For very short distance (short contact time) downstream the film can be treated as infinitely thick, since the mass transfer rate is not affected by the presence of the wall. In addition, in the interface vicinity the film velocity is approximately uniform and equal to $U_{max} = \frac{3}{2}U_{ave}$ (where U_{ave} is the average velocity). Equation (1.17) will be of the form:

$$U_{max} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial x_1} = D_{AB} \frac{\partial^2 C_A}{\partial y_1^2} \quad (1.18)$$

Where -

U_{max} - maximum velocity in the cross section

$$C_A(x_1=0) = 0 \quad (1.19)$$

$$C_A(y_1=0) = C_0 \quad (1.20)$$

$$C_A(y_1=\infty) = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

Where -

C_0 - initial concentration of specie A

The solution for this equation with these conditions is:

$$\frac{C_A}{C} = \operatorname{erfc} \sqrt{\frac{x_1^2 U_{\max}}{y_1 D_{AB}}}. \quad (1.22)$$

It should be emphasized that Higbie's solution to equation (1.18) is valid only when the concentration of the absorbate component is very low.

Extensive review/work has been carried out by Danckwerts [D1] for numerous cases of the partial differential equation (1.18) with different boundary conditions, for example, presence of resistance in the gas phase and existence of chemical reaction in the liquid film etc.

Arnold [A3] showed that the concentration level has significant effects on absorption rates. He solved the unsteady diffusion problem in a semi-infinite medium (see Exhibit 1.3).

Mass balance on component A yield:

$$\frac{\partial C_A}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial N_{Ax}}{\partial x_1} \quad (1.23)$$

Mass balance on component B yield:

$$\frac{\partial C_B}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial N_{Bx}}{\partial x_1} \quad (1.24)$$

Summation of equations (1.23) and (1.24) yields:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial (N_{Ax} + N_{Bx})}{\partial x_1} \quad (1.25)$$

Since the summation of N_{Bx} and N_{Ax} is constant (an ideal gas assumption under constant temperature and pressure conditions) it is possible to express it in the term of the flux of specie A at the interface.

Exhibit 1.3 Absorption at constant molar flux

$$N_{Ax} + N_{Bx} = N_{Ax} \Big]_{x=0} = \frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X^*)} \frac{\partial X_A}{\partial x} \Big]_{x=0} \quad (1.26)$$

Where -

X^* - equilibrium mole fraction at the liquid interface

Substituting equation (1.26) into molar flux equation yield expression for N_{Ax} , which when substituted into equation (1.23) yields the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 X_A}{\partial x_1^2} + \left\{ \frac{1}{(1-X^*)} \frac{\partial X_A}{\partial x_1} \right\} \Big]_{x=0} \frac{\partial X_A}{\partial x_1} = \frac{1}{D_{AB}} \frac{\partial X_A}{\partial t} \quad (1.27)$$

With the boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} X_A(t=0) &= 0 \\ X_A(x=0) &= X^* \\ X_A(x=\infty) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1.28)$$

Using the definition of similarity variable

$$Z = \frac{x}{\sqrt{4D_{AB}t}} \quad (1.29)$$

equation (1.27) changes to

$$\frac{d^2\Xi}{dZ^2} - 2(Z-\Psi) \frac{d\Xi}{dZ} = 0. \quad (1.30)$$

Where -

$$\Xi = \text{ratio } \frac{X_A}{X^*}$$

and

$$\Psi = - \left. \frac{1}{2(1-X^*)} \frac{d\Xi}{dZ} \right]_{Z=0} \quad (1.31)$$

The solution of this system is:

$$\frac{(X_A - X^*)}{(1 - X^*)} = -\sqrt{\pi}\Psi \exp(\Psi^2) \operatorname{erf}(\Psi) - \operatorname{erf}(Z - \Psi) \quad (1.32)$$

Arnold's study is the first in accounting for the finite concentration level. Almost all the studies up to now fall to arrive to equation (1.16).

1.3.2.2 Film theory

The penetration theory can not be applied to finite time contact or alternatively to absorption over finite surface length. The wall presence affects the diffusion boundary layer growth. The velocity profile as well as the boundary conditions has to be considered. A remark about the notations which have been used here for y and y_1 : in the majority of the work which deals with the absorption into semi-infinite film y/y_1 is measured from the free interface into the film, while in the majority of the work which deals with the film theory the coordinate y/y_1 is measured from the solid wall into the film, toward the free interface. In this section the same convention have been adopted.

Pigford [P1] solved equation (1.17) for parabolic velocity profile. The suggested solution was based on infinite series.

In the same time, Vayzovov [V2] suggested a solution which is based on orthogonal functions. An extension of his work has been done by Olbrich [O1]. He solved equation (1.17) for different geometries which have certain similarity. Rotem and Nielson [R2] checked the effects of mass transfer in the flow direction. Their solution, which was obtained by using orthogonal functions, shows that for large Pe_m numbers (which is the situation in most cases) the term that represent the diffusion in the flow direction can be neglected.

$$Pe_m = Re \times Sc = \frac{\bar{u}h}{D_{AB}} = \frac{\Gamma}{\rho D_{AB}} \quad (1.33)$$

Where -

Sc - Schmidt number

Taitel, Bentwich and Tamir [T1] arrived at the same conclusion; in addition, they discussed the importance of the distance upstream. Tamir and Taitel [T2] checked the resistance at the interface by representing it by the third type of boundary condition. Using eigenfunctions and eigenvalues a solution is achieved. The results were compared to experimental work by Emmert and Pigford [E1] and a reasonable agreement has been shown.

1.3.3 Influence of the physical properties

A review of theoretical solutions which deal with cases where the diffusion coefficient depends on the concentration is given in Ames [A1]. The relationship between the diffusivity coefficient to concentration assumed to be power relation of the form $D_{AB} \propto C^n$. Then equation (1.18) will have the form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[C^n \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right] = \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \quad (1.34)$$

It should be noted that the diffusivity coefficient is not written because it is possible to "absorb" it in one of the variable. It is possible to solve this equation by substituting the variables into a different form in which a separation of variables can be applied and a solution can be achieved. This method can be implemented only for $n > -1$. Moreover, this solution cannot be applied to all kind of boundary conditions.

Jameson [J1] checked the influence of linear relations between the physical properties and diffusion coefficient on the absorption. Further development have been done by Bentwich [B3]. Additional expansions have been carried out by Yih [Y1]. The authors assume that relation between the diffusivity coefficient and the concentration is exponential. The solution was carried out by separation of variables technique. The solution for the eigenfunctions and eigenvalues problem can be obtained by applying several numerical techniques. The conclusion that the authors arrive at is that this kind of relationship has significant effects on the mass transfer rates.

Absorption in Non-Newtonian fluids

A research on absorption in non-newtonian fluids was carried out by Chavan [C1]. He used equation (1.17) with a power velocity profile. This velocity profile is due the flow nature. The solution of this equation was obtained by using series expansion and numerically solved for the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. Applying streamlines coordinate simplifies the problem. This solution was compared to the penetration theory prediction. Yet, no comparison to any experimental data was

presented.

1.3.4 Absorption in wavy flow

When the flow is wavy laminar the surface starts to be wavy. Experiments show that transfer coefficients are higher than those expected, when calculated according to parabolic velocity profile and uniform thickness, sometimes the augmentation reaches hundreds percents. Some explanations have been suggested:

- 1) increase of the area of film free interface due the wavy nature of the flow,
- 2) free interface replenishment due to surface tension,
- 3) two dimensional velocity field-convection due to velocity component perpendicular to the flow direction,
- 4) turbulence increase (mixing motion) in the film.

Calculations which have been performed in the end of the fifties and the beginning of the sixties indicates that surface area increase can not be the main reason. The increase of the interfacial area, according to the calculations, can not be in hundreds percents. For example, Levich [L3] claims that the increase in surface area is only few percentage. He tried to solve the mass transfer problem by assuming superposition. The total mass transfer is combination of $- (C_1 + C_2)$. When the C_1 is represent the mass transfer due smooth film and C_2 represent the mass transfer due to waviness. The solution for the second term was achieved by using the penetration theory and so the transfer rate are found to increase as 15% relative to the smooth film transfer rate. Experimental verification of the above calculations have been done by Portalsky [P3]. He measured the surface change result from

the evolution of interfacial waves at the wave inception region.

Clearly, surface increase can not be the main reason for the increase of transfer rate in substantial percentage, but a different mechanism must exist. Banerjee et al [B1] suggested the reasoning that explains the difference between the theory and experiments as being caused by circulation induced due the movement of the wave. Verification of this theory can be carried out by relating to the experimental results of Brauner and Moalem [B9]. These results show a connection between the local transfer coefficient on the wall to where by wave phenomenon, wave cycle followed by the same cycle in local transfer coefficient. These experiments show connection between the diffusivity coefficient on the wall to wave phenomenon. This relationship indicates penetration of circulation, which is caused by the wave movement, up to wall. Moreover, it seems that it causes the renewing of the free interface. Portalsky [P2] tried to explain it by Kapitza's velocity distribution [K1] [K2]. Improvement of the last model carried out by Massot [M1] and Banerjee [B1].

Experimental results show that the relationship between the $K_L \propto D_{AB}^{5/8}$, where K_L - mass transfer coefficient and D_{AB} - molecular diffusion coefficient. This relationship is based on the experimental results of Emmert et al [E1] and others in the range $150 < Re < 800$. This relation is based on the physical model and not on the solution of exact equation. Pennev et al [P3] solved the two dimensional momentum equation with continuity equation numerically. It turned out that a discrepancy exist between the last solution to the Portalsky's theory even though the theory gave results which are closer to reality. The explanation which was suggested by Ruckenstien [R3] is the existence of

velocity perpendicular to flow direction. This idea when used in a linear model yields an augmentation compared smooth film of 30% . The solution of the non linear equations shows increase up to 100% and more. The increase can be represented by the following factor:

$$\Pi = f \left[\frac{g^{1/2} \Phi^{7/6}}{\rho^{4/3} \nu^{7/6} \sigma^{1/2}} \right]. \quad (1.35)$$

This model is in agreement with experimental work of Kamei et al [K3].

There are limitations on using the penetration theory for laminar film. It is clear that this limitations are stronger for wavy laminar film, therefore more sophisticated model is needed. Beschkov et al [B4] develop a model which describes the mass transfer for short and long exposure. The solution is obtained numerically with the assumption of two dimensional waves and isothermal absorption. Itzhak [I2] use the model suggested by Brauner and Moalem of wavy film flow to predict the mass transfer phenomena associated with developed wavy film flow. Wider review can be found in Oliver [O2], Grossman [G1], Mudawwer [M4], Dukler [D2], Yih [Y2], Zfati [Z1], and another extended survey can be found in Itzhak [I2].

1.3.5 Mass transfer in turbulent flow

Many researchers agree that when Reynolds number reaches $Re \approx 200$ turbulence starts to appear and around $Re \geq 1600$ flow becomes totally turbulent. Clearly, the equations that describe the laminar flow are not valid any more. The equations which have to be solved are the whole momentum equations. These equations are complicated mathematically, therefore the approach to the solution is development of correlations and models. There are many numerical studies which have been reviewed

by Bin [B5].

Most for the models of heat, mass and momentum transfer are based on the idea that a high percentage of the transfer is caused by eddy diffusivity. It is widely accepted that molecular coefficient D_{AB} should be replaced by a $D_{AB} + \epsilon$ where the eddy diffusivity, ϵ depends on y . The eddy diffusivity is usually larger than D_{AB} by order of magnitude (D_{AB} represent the molecular diffusivity). Therefore, instead of the full momentum equations the following equation is conventually solved.

$$U_x(y) \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\left(D_{AB} + \epsilon(y) \right) \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y} \right] \quad (1.36)$$

The film thickness is calculated by one of the methods described in the hydrodynamical part (section 1.2.4).

1.4 Simultaneous mass and heat transfer

In many cases, mass transfer is associated with simultaneous heat transfer. A large number of researchers dealt with the mass transfer phenomena but neglected the thermal effect which may be of importance. For example, absorption of ammonia into water and absorption of water vapor into brines. In these processes the absorption process is accompanied by heat release. The heat transfer affects the mass transfer in different ways. First: heat transfer, or more precisely, the change in the temperature in the film changes the physical properties, second: the temperature influences the equilibrium at the interface. Obviously, the process is dualistic which means also that mass transfer affects the heat transfer rates. Mass transfer is sometimes also accompanied by heat release and in this way it changes the boundary conditions for the heat transfer problem. There are other

possible ways for interaction: heat transfer due to the concentration gradient and mass transfer due temperature gradient thermodiffusion effect). There are additional reasons for the above coupling, e.g. existence of chemical reaction, etc. Because of the wide scope of this problem the discussion here will be mostly on the coupling due the changes in the boundary conditions.

1.4.1 Models of semi-infinite medium (penetration theory)

Being aware of the difficulties in solving only mass transfer problems, it is easy to understand the difficulties associated with solving coupled heat and mass transfer problems. The conventional approach is to write a simplified model, which later on may lead to more sophisticate models. Chiang and Toor's model [C2] was one of the first models which was suggested in the early sixties. The researches dealt with semi infinite medium. In this medium, ammonia is absorbed into water and during the absorption heat is released. The water level also changes its location due to mass accumulation and the equilibrium conditions are time dependent. Two partial differential equations describe the situation. In this case we have three unknowns, the temperature and concentration profiles and the location of the free interface. The third required equation is achieved by relating the mass transfer and the heat released to interface velocity. They solved the coupled equations by using an iterative method: assuming velocity profile the concentration profile was calculating, from which the new velocity profile was calculated. The solution has been achieved by repeating the process until convergent result, are obtained They assumed a linear relationship between the temperature and concentration for the equilibrium at the interface:

$$C^*(t) = bT^*(t) + d \quad (1.37)$$

Where -

- b,d - constants which depend on the temperature, pressure and material
- t - time
- T* - equilibrium temperature
- C* - equilibrium concentration

General discussion on this relationship can be found in Verma [V1], Shah [S1] and Grossman [G4]. This model, as Arnold's model, predicts higher mass transfer rates for higher absorbate concentrations.

A solution to the problem of non isothermal absorption assuming low penetration can be found in Grossman [G3]. Applying Higbie theory leads to two following equations.

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial y^2} \quad (1.38)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{Le} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \quad (1.39)$$

Where -

- Θ, Φ - normalized temperature and concentration, respectively
- x - normalized coordinate downstream
- y - normalized coordinate perpendicular to the stream.
- Le - Lewis number

With the following boundary conditions:

$$\Theta = \Phi = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0 \quad (1.40)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \Theta = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} \quad \text{at } y = \infty \quad (1.41)$$

and equilibrium condition (1.37) gets the form:

$$\Theta + \Phi = 1 \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (1.42)$$

and thermodynamical condition which means that all the latent heat

dedicated to heat the film.

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} = \Lambda \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \quad \text{at } y=0 \quad (1.43)$$

Where -

Λ - normalized specific latent heat

The solution for this system is:

$$\Theta = \frac{\Lambda}{\Lambda + \sqrt{Le}} \left[1 - \operatorname{erf} \sqrt{\frac{3y^2}{8x}} \right] \quad (1.44)$$

$$\Phi = \frac{\sqrt{Le}}{\Lambda + \sqrt{Le}} \left[1 - \operatorname{erf} \sqrt{\frac{3y^2}{Le 8x}} \right] \quad (1.45)$$

It needs to be mentioned that because of the simplicity of this solution it can be used as auxiliary tool to check asymptotic behavior in more complicate cases. Moreover, this solution can be used as a bass to solve more complicated cases.

1.4.2 Models of laminar flow

Clearly, models which describe semi infinite medium can not describe a real case which has a finite length. Among the firsts that dealt with finite medium were Grigoryeva and Nakoryakov [G1]. They assumed uniform velocity profile in the cross section (the average velocity). Similar equations to (1.38) and (1.39) have been obtained but with different boundary condition. The solution is obtained in terms of eigenfunctions and eigenvalues.

Improvement of this model using the same techniques was suggested by Grossman [G3]. In his model the assumption of constant velocity profile is abandoned and the velocity obtained for laminar flow is applied. The equations are the same as those used by Grigoryeva and

Nakoryakov's model, except the velocity profile. The boundary conditions are similar to those in the previous model [G1], only in this case the entrance temperature and the wall temperature are assume to be indential. The governing equation are:

$$\frac{3}{2} (2y+y^2) \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial y^2} \quad (1.46)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} (2y+y^2) \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{Le} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \quad (1.47)$$

where y is measured depth from the wall into the film.

The analytical solution of the system is obtained by serios which is converged very slowly. Similar results are obtained by numerical simulation. Moreover, the same author [G4] solved equation (1.46 and 1.47) by applying the integral method. For sufficiently short contact length diffusion boundary layer grows until it reaches to wall. From this point downstream the diffusion boundary layer thickness expands to the whole film accupies the enture film thickness and absorption continue until the liquid reaches saturation. The same happens for the heat transfer phenomena. Clearly, the situation can be such that the thermal boundary layer growth is "faster" than the concentration boundary layer and vice versa, according to to specific Sc number and Pr number, or the Le number. The integral method yields similar results to those obtained by the exact method. It is to be emphasized that all previous studies on non-isothermal absorption ([V1],[G3],[G4],[G2]) assumed infinite dilution of the absorbed component in the the film. Recently, Brauner [B15] employed the integral approach to study the effect of absorbate concentration level downstream the entry region. This work reconfirms the idea that the convective term has to be accounted for at high absorbate concentration level affecting an

augmentation of the transfer rates relative to those obtained for infinite absorbate dilution.

1.4.3 Models for turbulent flow

There are several models for simultaneous mass and heat transfer in turbulent flow. Many models are based on equations similar to (1.46) and (1.47) which are for laminar flow yet the change is in the effective diffusivity coefficient and heat transfer coefficient which are dependent also on the distance from the wall surface. Many researchers present the diffusion coefficient as summation of the laminar diffusion coefficient (molecular diffusion coefficient) with the turbulent eddy diffusion coefficient. Conventially, the turbulent diffusion coefficient is presented as some power of y . LeGoff et al [L2] suggested a model analogical to the equation (1.46) and (1.47) while the velocity profile was obtained as solution of "turbulent momentum equation" in the y direction. The equilibrium condition on the boundary was exactly like that in equation (1.37). A solution method [L3] is based on transforming the equations to Laplace space has been proposed. One of the conclusion drawn from this model is, that there exist an appreciable length along which the film behaves as it is infinite thickness.

Grossman et al [G6] extended the laminar model to turbulent absorption. Similar to most of the models for turbulent film, their model is based on the eddy diffusivity without taking into account the waviness phenomenon.

Brauner et al [B7] and [B8] examine the different aspects which are involved in absorption of the steam on brine film and show the importance of the integrating into the model the mass and heat transfer

phenomena with the effects of pressure loss and heat losses through the interface, temperature level at the wall and vapor pressure.

1.5 Experimental research

In this section some experimental studies and comparison between the experimental results to theoretical studies is reviewed. In reality it is very difficult to perform experiments in which all the theoretical models assumptions are fulfilled, and the one parameter, which is of interest, is isolated.

Taking the experimental approach, researchers have looked for the factors which control the absorption. Dimensional analysis helps to reduce the number of controlling factors to a minimum. Many researchers investigated experimentally the influence of the various parameters on the mass transfer. Emmert and Pigford [E1] reviewed the topic of absorption and desorption and find that there is almost no difference between the two.

Verma and Dlarcey [V1] performed many experiments of absorption of ammonia into water at low temperatures. They claimed that it is possible that the temperature at the interface changes due to the dilution of ammonia by the water, this dilution happens mostly at the interface (obviously). and consequently the mass transfer was reduced. This reduction is indeed predicted by the theoretical models of Grossman [G2], Nakoryakov et al [N1] and others. Emmert and Pigford [E1] used Lewis and Whitman presentation for the mass transfer coefficient which is given as (film theory):

$$K_L = \frac{D_{AB}}{h_N} \quad (1.48)$$

Won and Mills [W2] present the mass transfer coefficient K_L as a function of the following parameters

$$K_L = f \left[\sigma, D_{AB}, \rho, \nu, g, \Gamma \right] \quad (1.49)$$

Where -

σ , - surface tension, N/m

The relation which they suggested is in the form of $K_L \propto \sqrt{D_{AB}}$. This ratio reinforces the theory of renewal of the film surface. Experimental results of Kamei and Oishi [K3] represent the following ratio $K_L \propto Re^{0.7} D_{AB}^{0.556}$. Additionally, they concluded that the influence of surface tension on the transfer coefficient is negligible. Even though, their results were affected by temperature variation they claim that the main effect is due to viscosity change. As well, Bin [B5] claims, similarly to the above researches, that the surface tension has no influence on the mass transfer coefficient. Other researchers present the K_L in a different dimensionless form:

$$\frac{K_L}{g\nu^{1/3}} = \text{const} Re^n Sc^{-m} f \left[C_D \right] \quad (1.50)$$

Where C_D is Capillary Buoyancy number, defined in the following from:

$$C_D = \nu \left[\frac{\rho^3 g}{\sigma_3} \right]^{1/4} \quad (1.51)$$

For the last correlation it was found, see for example Won et al [W2] that for water and CO_2 $n = 3.49 C_D^{0.27}$ and $m=2$ and $f(C_D) = C_D^{-2}$. This correlation is restricted to $1000 < Re < 10,000$.

Other researchers represent the above relation (equation (1.50) in the following form:

$$\frac{K_L}{D_{AB}} \left[\frac{v^2}{g} \right]^{1/3} = \text{const} \text{Re}^n \text{Sc}^m \quad (1.52)$$

Where - m, n and the const are numbers obtained from experiments. For example, Bin's suggested [B5] $m=0.5, n=0.724$ and $\text{const}=6.89 \times 10^{-3}$. Lamourelle and Sandall [L1] suggest different values: $m=0.5$ and $n=1.506$. There is agreement among the researchers that K_L depend on square root of molecular the diffusivity, meaning $K_L \propto \sqrt{D_{AB}}$.

Burdukov at el [B16] performed experiments for the absorption of water vapor into a solution high concentration of lithium bromide and steam into brine. They compare the experimental results with model suggested by Nakoryakov at el [N1]. It turned out that the experimental transfer coefficient does not depend on the downstream distance. The explanation which they give is based on the wavy structure of the flow. They also checked the effect of noncondensable gases on the absorption (for example presence of air on the steam) and it turns out that the pressure of noncondensable gases reduces, significatly, the absorption rate. Their conclusion is that Nakoryakov's theory [N1] is reasonable but needs some refinement.

The effect of waviness on the local mass transfer rates at the solid wall was measured by Brauner and Moalem [B9]. This work compares the behavior of transfer rates obtained at the smooth entry region and those obtained downstream the wave inception region where the waves are already developed. As well, the effect of waviness on the local transfer coefficient has been observed. The transfer rates was found to reach a pick value when the wave is about its maximum height.

The scope of the work

In the light of the liturature review the need for analytical model is clear. The next two chapter are cunstructing a simple model one for the isothermal case and one for the non-isothermal case.

2. Isothermal absorption to film at high concentration

2.1 Theoretical model for isothermal absorption

This chapter deals with absorption of a gas into liquid film when the thermal effects are neglected (see Exhibit 2.1). The heat released during the hygroscopic condensation affects an increase of the the brine temperature, which influences the equilibrium interfacial concentration at the film interface. In some cases the heat interaction is small and the process may be considered isothermal. For the sake of simplicity and clarity , an isothermal case is considered here (and the coupling between the heat and mass is left for the next chapter).

Many researchers treat, as it was reviewed in chapter 1, the absorption problem in liquid film assuming that absorbate concentration is very low (for example see Higbie [H3]). In this chapter the significance of "absorbate concentration level" is discussed. The meaning of the "concentration level" is referring to the equilibrium and entry concentration which are not necessarily low relatively to other species. Schematic description of the physical problem is given in the Exhibit 2.1. A liquid with finite concentration of the absorbed material at $x_1=0$ streams in a given flow rate on a solid surface. The gaseous phase contain only the absorbate material. Then the material is absorbed into liquid through the interface at $y_1=0$. The assumptions that have been made in order to formulate the equations and to solve them are:

1. Absorption rate is very small compared to the film flow rate.

Exhibit 2.1 Absorption in a falling thin liquid film at different zones - description of the different concentration profiles

2. The liquid flow rate is constant and therefore the velocity profile and film thickness are constant (resulted from assumption 1).
3. The gas latent heat H_g is very small as compared with the heat capacity of the liquid, and the heat transfer to the gaseous phase is negligible.
4. The interface between the liquid and the gas is in a thermodynamic equilibrium.

5. The physical properties of film are constant. This assumption is reasonable when the absorption rate is small and the difference between the concentration in the interface and entrance is small.
6. No pressure loss in the x_1 direction (so, the equilibrium is not dependent on x_1).
7. Penetration depth is very small compared to the film thickness and therefore it can be assumed that film thickness is infinite in order to solve the absorption problem.
8. Constant concentration at the entrance (not dependent on y_1). This assumption does not impose any further restriction in the light of assumption 7. It should be emphasized that even if there is a concentration gradient in the entrance it is sufficient to take the first term in Taylor expansion series, which is constant.
9. The resistance in the gaseous phase is negligible.

2.2 The development of the governing equation

Mass balance on differential element on specie A (the absorbate) described in Exhibit 1.2. A steady state condition leads into the following equation (more explicit derivation can be found in chapter 1.3 in the literature review): Assuming there are no chemical reactions.

$$\frac{\partial N_{Ax_1}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial N_{Ay_1}}{\partial y_1} = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Where -

N_{Ax_1} - molar flux of specie A in x_1 direction, moles/sec-m²

N_{Ay_1} - molar flux of specie A in y_1 direction, moles/sec-m²

Recalling the molar flux equation in stationary coordinate is as the following (see further detailed explanation in Bird et al 1960 [B6]):

$$N_{Ax_1} = X_A (N_{Ax_1} + N_{Bx_1}) - D_{AB} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial x_1} \quad (2.2)$$

Where -

- C_A - absorbate concentration, moles/m³
- D_{AB} - diffusion coefficient of species A in B, m²/sec
- X_A - molar fraction of absorbate, $X_A = \frac{C_A}{C}$
- C - solution molar density, mole/m³
- N_{Bx_1} - molar flux of specie B in x_1 direction, moles/sec-m²

For liquid it is reasonable to assume that for large $Re \times Sc$ numbers (high Pe_m number) the mass transfer in the downstream direction is mostly due to convection and it is possible to assume that diffusion can be neglected. Under this condition equation (2.2) get the following form:

$$N_{Ax_1} = C_A U(y_1) \quad (2.3)$$

$U(y_1)$ - velocity in x_1 direction of function as y_1 , m/sec

For y_1 direction the following molar flux equation is:

$$N_{Ay_1} = X_A (N_{Ay_1} + N_{By_1}) - D_{AB} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} \quad (2.4)$$

Where -

- N_{By_1} - molar flux of specie B in y_1 direction, moles/sec-m²

The convective term in equation (2.4) can be omitted for either $X_A \rightarrow 0$ or $N_{Ay_1} = -N_{By_1}$, neither of which holds in the case of hygroscopic condensation. (For instance the minimum molar fraction of water which corresponds to saturated salt solution of $MgCl_2$, $LiBr$, $CaCl_2$, $NaOH$, is

about $X_A = 0.8$). On the other hand, the salt is not transferred, neither through the film free interface, nor through the solid wall, and thus by $N_{By_1} \sim 0$ may reasonably be assumed. Under these conditions, equation (2.4) yields:

$$N_{Ay_1} = -\frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X_A)} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} \quad (2.5)$$

Substituting equations (2.3) and equation (2.5) into equation (2.1) yields:

$$U(y_1) \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \left[\frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X_A)} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} \right] \quad (2.6)$$

For laminar flow it is widely accepted to assume Nusselt parabolic velocity profile which is $U(y_1) = 3/2 U_{ave} (1 - y_1^2)$. Where y_1 is measured from the interface into the wall. According to assumption 7 it is possible to substitute $U(y_1) = U(y_1=0) = U_{max}$ which is $3/2 U_{ave}$ equation (2.6) becomes:

$$U_{max} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \left[\frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X_A)} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} \right] \quad (2.7)$$

2.2.1 The boundary conditions

The boundary conditions are based on the following assumptions:

- 1) There is no mass transfer at the wall or the concentration far away from the free interface is constant and therefore it can be written:

$$\frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} (y_1 = \infty) = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

- 2) According to the assumptions (4) and (6) in paragraph 2.1 the pressure in gaseous phase and the temperature in liquid phase do not change downstream and therefore the equilibrium concentration is constant downstream. The mathematical condition is

$$C_A(x_1, y_1=0) = C^* \quad (2.9)$$

Where -

C^* - equilibrium concentration at given temperature and pressure,
 $\frac{\text{moles}}{\text{m}^3}$

- 3) The initial condition is a liquid at a given uniform concentration.
 (explanation to this condition is given in assumption 8):

$$C_A(x_1=0, y_1) = C_0 \quad (2.10)$$

Where -

C_0 - The concentration at the entrance, moles/m³

2.2.2 Dimensionless presentation

The differential equation (2.7) and the boundary conditions can be rewritten to a dimensionless form by defining the following dimensionless parameters:

$$x = \frac{x_1}{\delta} \quad y = \frac{y_1}{\delta} \quad \Phi = \frac{C-C_0}{C^*-C_0} \quad (2.11)$$

Where -

δ - the film thickness, m

Recalling that $X_A = C_A/C$, equation (2.7) becomes

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{Pe_m} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{1}{E\Phi+1-X_0} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \right] \quad (2.12)$$

Where -

$$Pe_m = \frac{\delta U_{max}}{D_{AB}}$$

$$E = \frac{(C_0-C^*)}{C}$$

$$X_0 = \frac{C_0}{C}$$

and the dimensionless boundary conditions are:

$$\Phi(x=0) = 0 \quad (2.13a)$$

$$\Phi(y=0) = 1 \quad (2.13b)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y}(y=\infty) = 0 \quad (2.13c)$$

2.2.3 Transformation similarity variables

Utilize Boltzman transformation (similarity variable) the two independent variables are combined into one and the partial differential equation is transformed into an ordinary differential equation. A similarity variable can be defined as:

$$z = \frac{y}{\sqrt{\frac{4x}{Pe_m}}} \quad (2.14)$$

In the term of the new variable equation (2.12) becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{1}{E\Phi+1-X_0} \frac{d\Phi}{dz} \right] + 2z \frac{d\Phi}{dz} = 0 \quad (2.15)$$

and the boundary conditions will have the form:

$$\Phi(x=0) = \rightarrow \Phi(z=\infty) = 0 \quad (2.16)$$

$$\Phi(y=0) = \rightarrow \Phi(z=0) = 1 \quad (2.17)$$

The boundary condition (2.13-c) is satisfied automatically. The detailed solution to equation (2.15) which is a non-linear ordinary differential equation is attached in appendix A.

2.3 Concentration profile solution

2.3.1 Solution of the ordinary differential equation

The solution can be presented as the following (see appendix A):

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{E} \left[\beta(z) - 1 + X_0 \right] \quad (2.18)$$

Where - $\beta(z)$ defined as the following:

$$\beta(z) = \exp \left[\alpha_1(z) \right] \quad (2.19)$$

$$\alpha_1(z) = C_3 \int_0^z \exp \left[\alpha_2(\xi) \right] d\xi + C_4 \quad (2.20)$$

$$\alpha_2(\xi) = - \int_0^\xi 2\xi' \beta(\xi') d\xi'. \quad (2.21)$$

Where -

$$\beta(\xi') = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\xi') \right] \quad (2.22)$$

The constants C_3 and C_4 are obtained from the boundary conditions.

Applying the boundary condition (2.17) yields:

$$1 = \frac{1}{E} \left[\exp(C_4) - 1 + X_0 \right] \quad (2.23)$$

or

$$C_4 = \ln \frac{C - C^*}{C} . \quad (2.24)$$

Applying boundary condition (2.16) yields the condition:

$$0 = \frac{1}{E} \left[\exp \left[\alpha_1(\infty) \right] - 1 + X_0 \right] \quad (2.25)$$

Where α_1 is defined in equation (2.20). Substituting equation (2.24) into equation (2.25) yields:

$$0 = (X_0 - X^*) (1 - X^*) \exp \left[C_3 \int_0^\infty \exp \left[\alpha_2(\xi) \right] d\xi(\infty) \right] - 1 + X_0 \quad (2.26)$$

Equation (2.26) is an algebraic equation for C_3 as a function of $\beta(\xi)$. For given $\beta(\xi)$ it is possible to solve it numerically for C_3 . For example for $\beta(\xi) = 1$.

$$C_3^{(1)} = \frac{\ln \frac{C - C_0}{C - C^*}}{\int_0^\infty \exp(-\xi^2) d\xi} \quad (2.27)$$

for any prescribed $\beta(\zeta)$:

$$C_3^{(n+1)} = \frac{\ln \frac{(C-C_0)}{(C-C^*)}}{\int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\int_0^\zeta 2\xi \beta(\xi) d\xi \right] d\zeta} \quad (2.28)$$

$$\beta(\xi)^{(n+1)} = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\xi) \right] \quad (2.29)$$

The upper index of C_3 and β is to indicate that it is not the exact C_3 and β but an approximation only.

It should be noted that β is unknown, therefore the solution method is iterative: starting with initial guess $\beta=1$, after applying an iterative method $\beta^{(n+1)}$ is calculated from equation (2.29) with the help of previous $\beta^{(n)}$. Again it should be noted that the value obtained is not exact but approximate only and denoted in the index " n " (higher index is corresponds to more precise value).

2.3.2 The solution algorithm

Equation (2.19) is Volterra integral equation for $\beta(\xi)$. It can be proved that this equation can be solved by an iterative method. Wider discussion is given in appendix A.

Calculation algorithm

- 1) First "guess" for $\beta(\xi)^{(n)} = 1, n=1$
- 2) Calculation of $C_3^{(1)}$ from equation (2.27) for the first estimate.
- 3) Calculation of $\beta^{(n+1)}$ from $\beta^{(n)}$ and $C_3^{(n)}$ values obtained from previous iteration by equation (2.29).
- 4) Calculation of $C_3^{(n+1)}$ from $\beta^{(n+1)}$ by using equation (2.28).

5) Checking for convergence of β and C_3

$$\left[\frac{\beta^{(n+1)} - \beta^{(n)}}{\beta^{(n)}} \right]^2 < \epsilon_1 \text{ and } \left[\frac{C_3^{(n+1)} - C_3^{(n)}}{C_3^{(n)}} \right]^2 < \epsilon_2 ,$$

these requirements are to be satisfied for any point in the field. Whenever one of the criteria are not satisfied, step 3 has to be repeated. If the two criteria are satisfied $\beta^{(n+1)}$ is the solution, and the iterative process is ended. It should be noted that during the runs that have been performed with $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 0.01$ and it has been found that when the first condition in 5 was satisfied the second condition was satisfied as well.

2.3.3 Solution for the infinite dilution case

In the case of low concentration the nonlinear problem becomes linear by using the assumption that X_A is small compared to 1 or $1 - X_A \sim 1$. The equation then (2.7) becomes:

$$U_{\max} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = \frac{D_{AB}}{\delta} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \quad (2.30)$$

with the following boundary conditions:

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} (y=\infty) = 0 \quad ; \quad \Phi(x=0) = 0 \quad ; \quad \Phi(y=0) = 1. \quad (2.31)$$

The solution to equation (2.30) was found by Higbie [H3]:

$$\frac{C_A}{C} = 1 - \operatorname{erf} \sqrt{\frac{x_1^2 U_{\max}}{y_1 D_{AB}}}. \quad (2.32)$$

This solution is suitable for prediction of the concentration profile which is obtained in absorption of sparingly soluble gases, like CO_2 and oxygen into watery film, due to low concentration of the absorbate compared to absorbent concentration.

2.4 Mass transfer rate at the interface

2.4.1 Mass transfer definition

One of the main interest in the mass transfer processes, beside finding the concentration profile as function of (x,y) , is to find the mass transfer rate into film at the interface.

Conventionally, the mass transfer rate can be expressed in terms of a dimensional mass transfer coefficient K , which in this case will be defined in the following way:

$$K(C^*-C_0) = N_{Ay_1}(y_1=0) = -\frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X_A)} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1}(y_1=0) \quad (2.33)$$

A corresponding Sh (the dimensionless mass transfer coefficient) can be defined:

$$Sh = \frac{Kx_1}{D_{AB}} \quad (2.34)$$

After substituting (2.33) into (2.34) yields:

$$Sh = \frac{-\frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1}(y_1=0) x_1}{(C^*-C_0)(1-X_A)} \quad (2.35)$$

2.4.2 Obtaining the mass transfer rate

Clearly, in order to obtain Sh number the concentration profile has to be known. Taking for example, a concentration profile which is obtained by assuming infinitely diluted solution, calculation of $\frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1}(y_1=0)$ from equation (2.32) and substituting it in equation (2.35) yields:

$$Sh^0 = \frac{K^0 x_1}{D_{AB}} = \sqrt{\frac{xPe_m}{\pi}} \quad (2.36)$$

Where Sh^0 is the dimensionless mass transfer coefficient for a case

where $X_A \rightarrow 0$. Using the concentration profile, which obtained in the solution to the equation (2.7), and utilizing the chain rule give Sh for the case of finite absorbate concentration.

$$\frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1}(y_1=0) = \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial \Phi} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial z} \frac{\partial z}{\partial y_1}(y_1=0) \quad (2.37)$$

Substituting equation (2.37) and the right derivatives into equation (2.35) yields:

$$Sh = \frac{C_3}{(X^* - X_0)} \sqrt{\frac{xPe_m}{4}} \quad (2.38)$$

Where C_3 is the value obtained in the iterative procedure (see section (2.3.2)). There is a special interest in the following ratio:

$$\Omega = \frac{Sh}{Sh^0} \quad (2.39)$$

The enhancement factor Ω represents the ratio of Sh in finite concentration (X_A with any arbitrary magnitude), to Sh^0 , which is obtained in infinite dilution (with assumption ($X_A \rightarrow 0$)). Substituting the right expressions into equation (2.39) yields:

$$\Omega = \frac{C_3}{2\sqrt{\pi}(X^* - X_0)} \quad (2.40)$$

2.5 Results, discussion and conclusions

From equation (2.15) it is seen that the isothermal absorption problem is affected by the following two parameters:

- 1) Concentration level, X_A , in the film which is expressed by the equilibrium concentration obtained in the terms of the absorption concentration X^* or X_0 . Due to the assumption of the model which requires low driving force for absorption, X^* and X_0 are of the same order of magnitude.

- 2) Normalized driving force of concentration - the difference between the equilibrium (at the interface) concentration and entrance concentration (X^*-X_0).

Figure 1 describes the concentration profiles as a function of similarity variable for several equilibrium concentrations for a constant absorption driving force (X^*-X_0) = 1%. From the Figure the following can be concluded.

- 1) When the equilibrium concentration approaches zero the error function is obtained, which is the solution to infinite dilution ($X_A \rightarrow 0$) (see appendix B). Clearly, the solution of equation (2.15) when X_A approaches zero should have the same results as the solution of Higbie (2.32) which is obtained by assuming low equilibrium concentration. Indeed, this convergence is described in Figure 1.
- 2) The concentration profile obtained for finite concentration is located above the corresponding value obtained for lower concentration. The meaning of "above" the solution for infinite dilution, is that the local concentration for finite concentration approaches the bulk concentration larger z . In other words, the boundary layer growth rate is much higher for higher concentration.
- 3) As well, it is possible to see that the rise in the concentration profile with the increase in the concentration level is not linear. Moreover, it is possible to see that the deviation from the solution infinite dilution is larger as the concentration level increases, which means, that small increase in the interface concentration leads to bigger deviation of the concentration profile from the corresponding solution obtained for infinite

absorbate dilution.

In appendix B the significance of C_3 was found. The β , function which was defined in equation (a.1), approaches for a small value of C_3 to the error function. The solution obtained by assuming low concentration is also an error function. One might conclude from here that for low concentration, C_3 has to be very small. Figure 7 describes C_3 as a function of the concentration level. The results obtained verify this conclusion. Small values of the absorbate concentration lead to smaller value of C_3 . It is possible to say the problem become more linear when C_3 is smaller.

Figure 2 shows comparison between the concentration profile which was obtained with the assumption of constant N_{By_1} stagnant (present work) and concentration profile obtained by assuming constant molar flux, Arnold [A3]. In section 1.3.2.1 it was detailed that Arnold's solution describes the transient absorption in an infinite long pipe. Indeed the geometry in Arnold's case is different from our case. However, transformation of the time scale into length scale in a constant molar flux model yields similar problems (similar transformation was suggested by Danckwerts [D1]). From Figure 2 it is shown that profiles have the same trends which means that when the concentration increases the profile "climbs" up. Moreover, it is possible to see that the profiles are almost identical for low concentrations. The meaning of this is that the assumption of constant molar flux and the assumption of $N_{By_1} \sim 0$ are interchangeable for low concentration (for example, at $z=1$ and concentration level of 30% the difference is 5.7% while the difference in 50% and the same z is 23%).

Figures 3 and 4 describe the effect of process driving force. The concentration profiles are those obtained for various entrance concentrations with X^* 's constant and equal to 50% and 80% respectively. The conclusion deduced from these results is that the solution depends mostly on the absorbate concentration level which is expressed by the equilibrium concentration. The influence of the driving force, (X^*-X_0) (the difference between the equilibrium concentration and entrance concentration) is relatively small.

It should be emphasized, that the physical properties of the liquid film (diffusion coefficient, density, viscosity, etc) are incorporated in Pe_m and to be taken according to appropriate concentrations (also for infinite dilution $X_A \ll 1$). Therefore, the effect of the "concentration level" on the solution, shown in the figures, describes the deviation from the assumption of infinite dilution $X_A \rightarrow 0$ in the solution of equation (2.7).

The impact of the equilibrium concentration on Sh_x is described in figure 6. The enhancement factor Ω , described in equation (2.40), expresses the ratio between the transfer coefficient in the present case (finite concentration) to transfer coefficient which obtained in the limit of low concentration case. In Figure 6, the results obtained for Ω as function of the concentration level and for various process driving forces are shown. From the graph it can be concluded that as the absorbate concentration level is higher, the transfer coefficient is bigger. Similarly to the results obtained by Arnold's work, the mass transfer coefficient is growing faster with increasing the concentration level.

In the solution, higher absorption rates are obtained for higher level of concentration. This may contradict assumption 1 stated in the development of the model. This assumption requires that the absorption rate is small relatively to the flow rate of liquid film. Therefore, there is a need to limit the solution range. The ratio between the absorption rate to the film flow rate given in equation (2.41):

$$1 \gg \frac{\rho N_{Ay_1}}{\Gamma C} = \frac{Sh \rho D_{AB}}{\frac{\mu}{\Gamma}} \frac{\delta}{x_1} \frac{(C^* - C_0)}{C} \quad (2.41)$$

the dimensionless presentation of equation (2.41)

$$1 \gg \frac{\rho N_{Ay_1}}{\Gamma C} = \frac{4 Sh (X^* - X_0)}{Pe_m x} \quad (2.42)$$

or

$$\Omega \gg \frac{\sqrt{x Pe_m}}{2 (X^* - X_0)} \quad (2.43)$$

where -

Γ - mass flow rate per unit width, [kg/sec-m]

μ - viscosity, [Kg/m-sec]

ρ - specific density, [Kg/m³]

Re - Reynolds number, $\frac{4\Gamma}{\mu}$

Sc - Schmidt number, $\frac{D_{AB}\rho}{\mu}$

therefore as long as this inequality the solution is valid. A typical range of Pe_m is 10^5 - 10^6 . Calculated results (based on equations (2.18) - (2.26) show that equation (2.43) is indeed satisfied.

Figure 5 describes the z which is obtained when Φ has dropped to a value of 1%. Since $z \propto \frac{y_1}{\sqrt{x_1}}$ or $\delta_c \propto z \sqrt{x_1}$ it is evident that increasing the absorbent concentration level results in an enhanced penetration of

the diffusion boundary layer into film. Yet, it should be kept in mind that the applicability of the solution is physically valid where $\frac{\delta_c}{\delta} \ll 1$.

Figure 6 also shows that concentration level has a dominate effect on the Ω , while the driving force has a marginal one. The corresponding ratio of Sherwood numbers is described in Figure 6 (equation (2.40)). This Figure shows clearly the mass transfer coefficient (or Sh number) based on the assumption of low concentration $X_A \sim 0$ gives significantly lower coefficient than that obtained by the present model. Similar results have been obtained by Arnold under the assumption of constant molar flux [A3] when the concentration rises the magnitude of the transfer coefficient grow also.

3. Non isothermal absorption to film at high concentration

3.1 Theoretical model for simultaneous heat and mass transfer

In the previous chapter the isothermal absorption has been discussed where the thermal effects were omitted. This chapter deals with the non isothermal absorption, and as a result a simultaneous heat and mass transfer occurs. The mass transfer is almost always accompanied by heat transfer which sometimes can be neglected like in the case of air absorbed by water. However, the heat of absorption is to be considered in other cases, like vapor absorption by brines. Therefore, the heat transfer which is associated with the mass transfer can not be neglected.

The system is similar to the one which is described in the previous chapter in Exhibit 2.1. The mass transfer equation is also suitable for this case. In addition, a heat transfer equation is also needed. All the assumptions from chapter 2 are applicable in this case except assumption 3 which means that H_v of the vapor is small compared to heat capacity of liquid.

3.2 Developing the heat equation

The situation described in Exhibit (3.1) is for steady state and no heat sources. The entering heat to the element has to be equal to amount of heat leavening. Writing a summation of the components which enter and leave the element and performing the usual limiting process as the volume element becomes infinitesimally small, yield the well know 2-D heat equation:

Exhibit 3.1 Energy balance on an element

$$\frac{\partial [T v(x_1)]}{\partial y_1} + \frac{\partial [T u(y_1)]}{\partial x_1} = \alpha \left[\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_1^2} \right] \quad (3.2)$$

where -

α - liquid diffusivity, $k/\rho C_p$, [m²/sec]

For large $Pe_T = \frac{U_{max} \delta}{\alpha}$ number it can be assumed that the heat transfer in

x_1 direction is mostly by convection, and, the term $\frac{\partial [T u(x_1)]}{\partial y_1} \ll$

$\frac{\partial [T v(y_1)]}{\partial x_1}$. This is mostly due to $u(y_1) \gg v(x_1)$. Also consistent with the

assumption of constant film thickness, the energy convection due to the bulk flow in the y_1 direction is small compare to convection in the downstream direction. The solution for the "short contact time" enable one to assume constant velocity profile: i.e. $u(y_1)$ change to U_{max} which is $\frac{3}{2}U_{ave}$ in laminar flow. Hence, equation (3.1) reduces to:

$$U_{max} \frac{\partial T y_1}{\partial x_1} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y_1^2}. \quad (3.2)$$

3.2.1 Boundary conditions

The initial conditions are:

$$T=T_0 \quad \text{and} \quad C=C_0 \quad \text{at} \quad x_1=0 \quad (3.3)$$

The boundary conditions at infinity are assumed to be:

$$T=T_0 \quad \text{and} \quad C=C_0 \quad \text{at} \quad y_1=\infty \quad (3.4)$$

It is assumed that thermodynamical equilibrium exist on the free boundary:

$$T=T^*(P_v, C^*) \quad \text{and} \quad C=C^* \quad \text{at} \quad y_1=0 \quad (3.5)$$

Where C^* is the absorbate interfacial concentration at the temperature T^* which is in equilibrium with pressure P_v which exist at the interface. Note that though T^*, C^* are in fact unknown, they are related to each other by both temperature-concentration-pressure equilibrium and they are function of the distance x_1 .

$$f(T^*, C^*) = P_v = \text{const} \quad \text{at} \quad y_1=0 \quad (3.6)$$

Additionally, both of them are related to absorption rate through the interface $N_{Ay_1}^*$, which also is unknown, by the following relations:

$$-\frac{D_{AB}}{(1-X_A)} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y_1} = N_{Ay_1}^* \quad \text{at} \quad y_1=0 \quad (3.7)$$

$$-k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y_1} = N_{Ay_1}^* H_a(T^*, C^*) \quad \text{at} \quad y_1=0 \quad (3.8)$$

Where -

- H_a - heat of absorption (per mole of the vapor) in the liquid.
wider discussion can be found in Grossman [G3], [kJ/kmol]
- $N_{A_{Y_1}}^*$ - molar flux at the interface, [moles/sec-m²]

Equation (3.6) describes the equilibrium relationship on the interface. Equations (3.7) and (3.8) describe the absorption rate and heat transfer rate at the interface, respectively. Clearly, in order to solve the model, the function for $f(T^*, C^*)$ has to be specified. For wide range of materials, it is possible to describe the relationship between the concentration and temperature at equilibrium as linear for constant vapor pressure. Detailed discussions can be found in several resources as it is mentioned in the literature review (see section 1.4.1). Therefore, the relationship can be written:

$$C^* = bT^* + d \quad (3.9)$$

where -

b, d - constants which depend on the materials and the pressure.
Additionally, the latent heat is assumed to be independent on the concentration and temperature. This assumption is a good approximation for materials with low molecular weight like water (see Grossman [G3]).

$$H_a = \text{const} \quad (3.10)$$

Clearly, equations (3.6)-(3.8) represent the coupling between the heat and mass transfer mechanisms.

3.2.2 Dimensionless presentation

The following dimensionless variables are defined:

$$x = \frac{x_1}{Pe_T \delta} \quad y = \frac{Y_1}{\delta} \quad (3.11)$$

Where -

δ - film thickness

$$\Theta = \frac{T-T_0}{T_e-T_0}$$

$$\Phi = \frac{C-C_0}{C_e-C_0}$$

Pe_T - thermal Peclet number, $\frac{U_{max}\delta}{\alpha}$

C_0 - entry concentration

C_e - the equilibrium concentration at the entry temperature

T_e - the equilibrium temperature at the entry concentration

Note that the definitions of C_e and T_e have a physical significance. T_e is interface temperature which would be obtained when the interface concentration is maintained at the entry temperature and vapor pressure P_v . C_e is interface concentration which would be obtained when the interface temperature is maintained at the entry concentration and vapor pressure P_v . The equilibrium temperature $T^*=T^*(C^*,P_v)$ includes the boiling point elevation corresponding to the brine concentration, C^* which is in equilibrium with its vapor at pressure, P_v . In fact T^*-T_0 is a useful measure of the nominal available temperature driving force for the hygroscopic condensation process. According to equation (3.9) the following relationship can be written:

$$C_e = bT_0 + d \quad (3.12a)$$

$$T_e = bC_0 + d \quad (3.12b)$$

(Note that x in this chapter is not the same x as in the previous chapter but differ in factor of Pe_T) After substituting these definitions (3.11) into are substituted equations (3.2) and (2.7) and the following equations

are obtained (note that z in this chapter is differ in factor of Pe_T):

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial y^2} \quad (3.13)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = Le \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{1}{E\Phi+1-\frac{C_0}{C}} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \right] \quad (3.14)$$

Where -

Le - Lewis number, D_{AB}/α , Pe_T/Pe_m

E - $(C_0-C_e)/C$

The boundary conditions have the form:

$$T(x_1=0) = T_0 \rightarrow \Theta(x=0) = 0 \quad (3.15)$$

$$C(x_1=0) = C_0 \rightarrow \Phi(x=0) = 0 \quad (3.16)$$

$$T(y_1=\infty) = T_0 \rightarrow \Theta(y=\infty) = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

$$C(y_1=\infty) = C_0 \rightarrow \Phi(y=\infty) = 0 \quad (3.18)$$

On the free interface also the following conditions exist:

$$T(y_1=0) = T^* \rightarrow \Theta(y=0) = \Theta^* \quad (3.19)$$

$$C(y_1=0) = C^* \rightarrow \Phi(y=0) = \Phi^* \quad (3.20)$$

After substituting the dimensionless variables into equations (3.6), (3.7) and (3.8) the following equations are obtained:

$$f(\Theta^*, \Phi^*) = 0 \quad (3.21)$$

$$\eta^* = \frac{N_{Ay}^* \delta}{D_{AB}(C_e-C_0)} \quad (3.22)$$

$$-\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} = \eta^* \Lambda \quad (3.23)$$

Where -

η^* - dimensionless molar flux of absorbate at the interface

Λ - dimensionless heat of condensation-absorption, $\frac{LeH_a(C_e-C_0)}{\rho C_p(T_e-T_0)}$

Utilizing the linear relationship between the temperature and concentration, and substituting the definitions for Φ and Θ yields:

$$\Phi^* + \Theta^* = 1 \quad (3.24)$$

Using the assumption, Λ equal constant, yields:

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} = \frac{\Lambda}{E\Phi+1-X_0} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \quad (3.25)$$

where -

$$X_0 = \frac{C_0}{C}$$

$$E = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C}$$

3.2.3 Transformation similarity variables

Using the same method as in the previous chapter and defining:

$$z = \frac{y}{2\sqrt{x}} \quad (3.26)$$

(note that in present chapter z E are differ from previous chapter) equations (3.13) and (3.14) can be written in the following form:

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dz^2} + 2z \frac{d\theta}{dz} = 0 \quad (3.27)$$

$$\text{Le} \frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{1}{E\Phi+1-X_0} \frac{d\Phi}{dz} \right] + 2z \frac{d\Phi}{dz} = 0 \quad (3.28)$$

Equation (3.3) and (3.28) are ordinary differential equations which need to satisfy the the following boundary conditions:

$$\Phi(x=0) = 0 \quad \rightarrow \quad \Phi(z=\infty) = 0 \quad (3.29a)$$

$$\Theta(x=0) = 0 \quad \rightarrow \quad \Theta(z=\infty) = 0 \quad (3.29b)$$

$$\Theta + \Phi = 1 \quad \text{at } z=0 \quad (3.29c)$$

$$\frac{d\Theta}{dz} = \frac{\Lambda}{E\Phi+1-X_0} \frac{d\Phi}{dz} \quad \text{at } z=0 \quad (3.29d)$$

The boundary conditions (3.17) and (3.18) are satisfied automatically. General discussion can be found in Ames [A1].

3.3 Solution of the concentration and the temperature profiles

3.3.1 Solution of the differential equations

The solution to equation (3.28) can be presented as the following (see Appendix A):

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{E} \left[\beta(\zeta) - 1 + x_0 \right] ; \quad \zeta = \frac{z}{\sqrt{Le}} \quad (3.30)$$

Where - $\beta(\zeta)$ defined as the following:

$$\beta(\zeta) = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\zeta) \right] \quad (3.31)$$

$$\alpha_1(\zeta) = C_3 \int_0^{\zeta} \exp \left[\alpha_2(\xi) \right] d\xi + C_4 \quad (3.32)$$

$$\alpha_2(\xi) = - \int_0^{\xi} 2\xi' \beta(\xi') d\xi'. \quad (3.33)$$

Where -

$$\beta(\xi') = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\xi') \right] \quad (3.34)$$

The unknown constants C_3, C_4 are derived from the boundary conditions in equations (3.29a-d) which are coupled with the energy equation, equation (3.3) the solution of which is given by

$$\Theta = C_1 \operatorname{erf}(z) + C_2. \quad (3.35)$$

Note that while the temperature solution obtained in terms of z , as in equation (3.35) the concentration solution is obtained in terms of $z/\sqrt{Le}$, equation (3.30). Utilizing the boundary condition of equation (3.29b) in equation (3.35), yields

$$C_1 = -C_2 \quad (3.36)$$

Substituting the Φ, Θ solutions of equations (3.30) and (3.35) into equations (3.29c) and (3.29d) yields a relationship between C_2 and C_4

$$C_2 + \frac{\exp(C_4) - 1 + x_0}{E} = 1 \quad (3.37)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{\Lambda C_3}{E \sqrt{Le}}. \quad (3.38)$$

Combining equations (3.36)-(3.38) yields

$$\exp(C_4) = 1 - X_e + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}} C_3. \quad (3.39)$$

Applying boundary conditions (3.29a) while utilizing equation (3.39) results in the following relation for C_3 :

$$\left[1 - X_e + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}} C_3 \right] \beta(\infty) + [X_0 - 1] = 0 \quad (3.40)$$

Equations (3.30)-(3.40) are solved iteratively: starting with a uniform distribution, $\beta(z)=1$, equation (3.40) is solved for C_3 , which in turn is utilized in equations (3.39) and (3.31) to obtain a new β . Equations (3.35)-(3.37) then yield the corresponding solutions for $\Theta(z)$. Less than ten iterations have been usually found sufficient to yield convergence. Note that the solution is obtained for a given set of X_0 , (X^*-X_0) , and $\frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}}$.

Equation (3.40) is an algebraic equation for C_3 as a function of $\beta(\zeta)$. For given $\beta(\zeta)$ it is possible to solve it numerically for C_3 . For example for $\beta(\zeta)=1$.

$$C_3^{(1)} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\sqrt{Le}}{\Lambda} (X_e - X_0) \quad (3.41)$$

for any prescribed $\beta(\zeta)$:

$$C_3^{(n+1)} = \frac{\frac{1-X_0}{\beta(\infty)} + X_e - 1}{\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}}} \quad (3.42)$$

$$\beta(\zeta)^{(n+1)} = \exp \left[\alpha_1^{(n)}(\zeta) \right] \quad (3.43)$$

The upper index of C_3 and β is to indicate that it is not the exact C_3 and β but an approximate only.

It should be noted that β is unknown, therefore the solution method is iterative: starting with initial guess $\beta=1$, after applying an iterative method $\beta^{(n+1)}$ is calculated from equation (3.43) with the help

of previous $\beta^{(n)}$. Again it should be noted that the value obtained is not exact but approximate only and denoted in the index " $^{(n)}$ " (for convergent process when the index is higher it is more precise).

3.3.2 The solution algorithm

Equation (2.2) is Volterra integral equation for $\beta(\xi)$. It can be proved that this equation can be solved by an iterative method. A wider discussion is given in Appendix A.

Calculation algorithm

- 1) First "guess" for $\beta(\xi)^{(n)} = 1, n=1$
- 2) Calculation of $C_3^{(1)}$ from equation (3.41) for the first estimate.
- 3) Calculation of $\beta^{(n+1)}$ from $\beta^{(n)}$ and $C_3^{(n)}$ values obtained from previous iteration by equation (3.43).
- 4) Calculation of $C_3^{(n+1)}$ from $\beta^{(n+1)}$ by using equation (3.42).
- 5) Checking for convergence of β and C_3

$$\left[\frac{\beta^{(n+1)} - \beta^{(n)}}{\beta^{(n)}} \right]^2 < \epsilon_1 \text{ and } \left[\frac{C_3^{(n+1)} - C_3^{(n)}}{C_3^{(n)}} \right]^2 < \epsilon_2 ,$$

these requirements are to be satisfied for any point in the field. Whenever one of the criteria are not satisfied, step 3 has to be repeated. If the two criteria are satisfied $\beta^{(n+1)}$ is the solution, and the iterative process is ended. It should be noted that during the runs which have been performed $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 10E-6$ and it has been found that when the first condition in 5 is satisfied the second condition is satisfied as well.

3.3.3 Solution for the infinite dilution case

In the case of absorption of sparingly soluble gases, $1 \gg X_A$ the term of $(1-X_A)$ equation (3.41) degenerate to 1. The formulation leading to equations (3.2) - (3.28) is reduced to the known conventional heat and mass diffusion equations.

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial y^2} \quad (3.44)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{Le} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \quad (3.45)$$

with the following boundary conditions:

$$\Theta = \Phi = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0 \quad (3.46)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \Theta = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} \quad \text{at } y = \infty \quad (3.47)$$

and the condition (3.9) take the form:

$$\Theta + \Phi = 1 \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (3.48)$$

and thermodynamical condition which means that all the heat of absorption is dedicated to heat the film.

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} = \Lambda \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \quad \text{at } y=0 \quad (3.49)$$

where -

Λ - normalized specific heat absorption

The analytical solution to equations (44)-(49) has been given by Grossman [G3]:

$$\Theta^0 = \frac{\Lambda}{\Lambda + \sqrt{Le}} \left[1 - \text{erf}(z) \right] \quad (3.50)$$

$$\Phi^0 = \frac{\sqrt{Le}}{\Lambda + \sqrt{Le}} \left[1 - \text{erf}(z/\sqrt{Le}) \right] \quad (3.51)$$

3.4 Heat and Mass transfer at the interface

3.4.1 Heat and Mass transfer definition

Having established the Φ , Θ solutions, the mass transfer coefficient at the film free interface is defined by

$$K = \frac{N_{Ay}|_{y=0}}{(C^*-C_0)} = -\left. \frac{D_{AB}C}{\delta(C-C^*)} \frac{1}{\Phi^*} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0}; \quad (3.52)$$

where -

$$\Phi^* = \frac{C^*-C_0}{C_e-C_0}.$$

The heat transfer coefficient due to non-isothermal absorption at the free interface is defined by

$$h = \frac{q|_{y=0}}{(T^*-T_0)} = -\left. \frac{k}{\delta} \frac{1}{\Theta^*} \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0}; \quad (3.53)$$

where -

$$\Theta^* = \frac{T^*-T_0}{T_e-T_0}.$$

k - thermal conductivity of liquid [$\frac{Kw}{m-K}$]

3.4.2 Obtaining the heat and mass transfer rates

Utilizing equations (3.30) and (3.39) in equation (3.52) the corresponding local and average Sherwood numbers are obtained

$$Sh = \frac{Kx_1}{D_{AB}} = \frac{C_3C}{(C-C^*)(C^*-C_0)} \left[C-C_e + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{C_3C\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{xPe_T^2}{4Le}} \quad (3.54)$$

$$\overline{Sh} = \frac{\overline{Kx_1}}{D_{AB}} = \frac{1}{x_1} \int_0^{x_1} Sh(x_1') dx_1' = 2Sh(x) \quad (3.55)$$

Substituting the solution for the temperature profile given in equations (3.35)-(3.38) yields

$$h = \rho C_p \sqrt{\frac{U_{max} \alpha}{\pi x_1}} \quad (3.56)$$

The corresponding local and average Nusselt numbers are given by

$$Nu = \frac{hx_1}{k} = \sqrt{\frac{x}{\pi} Pe_T^2} ; \bar{Nu} = \frac{\bar{h}x_1}{k} = 2Nu. \quad (3.57)$$

Based on equations (3.50) and (3.51) the local dimensional and non dimensional mass and heat transfer coefficients, corresponding to infinite dilution, are given by

$$K^0 = \frac{-D_{AB} \frac{\partial C_A}{\partial y} \Big|_{y=0}}{C_e - C_0} = \left. -\frac{D_{AB}}{\delta} \frac{1}{\Phi^*} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \right]_{y=0} \quad (3.58)$$

$$K^0 = \sqrt{\frac{D_{AB} U_{max}}{\pi x_1}} \quad (3.59)$$

$$Sh^0 = \frac{K^0 x_1}{D_{AB}} = \sqrt{\frac{x Pe_T^2}{4 Le}} \quad (3.60)$$

$$h^0 = \rho C_p \sqrt{\frac{U_{max} \alpha}{\pi x_1}} \quad (3.61)$$

$$Nu^0 = \frac{h^0 x_1}{k} = \sqrt{\frac{x}{\pi} Pe_T^2} \quad (3.62)$$

Comparison of equations (3.60) and (3.62) with equations (3.53) and (3.57) indicates that while the mass transfer coefficients at the film free interface for infinite and finite dilution are different the heat transfer coefficients for the two cases are identical. This is in view of the fact that the temperature fields obtained by equations (3.35) and (3.50) are both described by error-function distribution. The constants in equations (3.35) and (3.50) however, are different, due to coupling with the mass transfer problem, which is affected by the dilution level $(1 - X_A)$. Note also that both the heat and mass flux change with the dilution level due to the variation of the driving forces at the free interface.

The effect of finite dilution, as represented by $X_A = \frac{C_A}{C} \neq 0$ in equation (3.14), evolves from retaining the convective term in equation (2.7). An enhancement factor Ω is thus introduced, which expresses the ratio between the actual absorption mass transfer coefficient, K , and that obtained under the assumption of infinite dilution, K^0

$$\Omega = \frac{K}{K^0} = \frac{Sh}{Sh^0} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} C_3 \frac{\left[1 - X_e + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} C_3 \frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}} \right]}{(X^* - X_0)(1 - X^*)} \quad (3.63)$$

It is also to be noted that the assumption of low absorption rate implies that $\rho \delta N_{Ay_1} / \Gamma C \ll 1$. In terms of Sh and Sh^0 , as defined in equations (3.54) and (3.63), this restriction reads

$$\Omega = \frac{Sh}{Sh^0} \ll \frac{2\pi}{3} \frac{Sh^0}{2(X_e - X_0)} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{(X_e - X_0)} \sqrt{\frac{x Pe_T^2}{Le}} \quad (3.64)$$

A typical range of Pe_T/Le is $10^5 - 10^6$ (note that $\frac{Pe_T}{Le} = Pe_m$ similar to chapter 2). Calculated results (based on equations (3.30)-(3.40) show that equation (3.64) is indeed satisfied.

3.5 Results and Discussion

As is indicated by equations (3.30)-(3.35), the solution for the non-dimensional concentration of the absorbate is determined by both the interfacial concentration level, X_e , and the driving force $(X_e - X_0)$. In the non-isothermal case, $\Lambda \neq 0$, and thus a third parameter, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$, is involved. The calculated results are presented, in what follows, in terms of these three non-dimensional parameters. However, for the purpose of comparing Θ and Φ for an identical z point, it is required to specify $\sqrt{Le}$ as well (see equations (3.30), (3.35) or (3.50) and (3.51)).

Before going into further discussion the following definition should be mentioned and emphasized, the difference between two

definitions of the equilibrium at the interface. The first, C_e is interface concentration which would be obtained when the interface temperature is maintained at the entry concentration and vapor pressure P_v . The second, C^* is the interfacial concentration which obtain the real case (when the temperature and concentration are in there real values (equation (3.9)).

Figures 8-19 show the solutions for the dimensionless temperature and absorbate concentration distributions at various concentration levels, X_e , and specified nominal driving force, $X_e - X_0$ or heat of absorption parameter, $\frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}}$. As is shown in Figure 11-13, for large z (large x or small y) the temperature in the absorbing film is that of the inlet, therefore $\Theta \rightarrow 0$. As the equilibrium concentration at the interface is higher than C_0 due to dilution caused by the process of condensation, the equilibrium interfacial temperature (for constant P_v) is always lower than T_e , hence Θ at the interface ($z=0$) is smaller than 1. For a relatively low concentration level ($X_e = 0.21$) the temperature profile approaches that for infinite dilution [H3] [G3] as given by equation (3.50) for all values of $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$. Increasing the concentration level, $X_e=0.81$ as in Figures 11-13, affects significantly higher interfacial temperature due to higher absorption rates (Figures 22 and 23), thus Θ deviates relative to that of infinite dilution, particularly at small z .

The absorbate distribution demonstrates similar trends as depicted in Figures 8-10 and 14-19. For large ζ , the concentration goes to C_0 or $\Phi \rightarrow 0$, while at the interface, $\Phi < 1$, indicating the effect of coupling between heat and mass transfer; if the temperature at the interface is constant at the entry level, T_0 , as in isothermal

absorption, the equilibrium interfacial concentration (with negligible pressure losses) remains constant at C_e or $\Phi^* = 1$. This is demonstrated in Figure 10 which relates to isothermal absorption, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 0.2 - 0$. As the concentration level increases, the solutions, in general, deviate from the low-penetration solutions for infinite dilution, equations (3.50) and (3.51), which under isothermal conditions reduce to Higbie's well-known solution [H3]. For non-isothermal absorption, Figures 8-10, the interfacial concentration, at $z=0$, decreases with increasing concentration level, corresponding to the interfacial temperature rise noted in Figures 11-13. However, for larger z , Φ increases with increasing concentration level, indicating a deeper penetration of diffusion boundary layer.

The effect of heat and mass coupling parameter, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$, is demonstrated through Figures 14-17 and 20-21. For low heat of absorption or high Le , the heat interaction can be considered small (mass transfer controlled), and isothermal solutions are approached whereby $\Theta \rightarrow 0$ (Figure 11) and $\Phi^*(\xi=0) \rightarrow 1.0$ (Figure 16). As $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$ increases, the interfacial equilibrium temperature increases (Figures 12-13) while the corresponding concentration decreases (Figures 14-16). For high $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$, heat transfer dominates and therefore the effect of the concentration level diminishes (Figures 11 and 14-16). On the other hand, for lower $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$, where mass transfer dominates, the concentration level is of significant effect on both the temperature (Figures 12-13) and concentration (Figures 14-16) profiles as indicated by the deviation from the corresponding solutions for infinite dilution.

Figure 17 represents the interfacial concentration as functions of the coupling parameter and concentration level. Consistent with Figures

8-10, the interfacial concentration decreases with both the concentration level and $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$. As is indicated by the figure, the solutions for finite dilution are bounded by that of infinite dilution, as given by equation (3.50) for $\zeta = 0$. Note that $\Theta^* = 1 - \Phi^*$.

The results presented so far relate the temperature and concentration profiles at constant driving force, $(X_e - X_0) = 0.01$. As in the case of isothermal absorption also here it is found that the effects of the driving force on the Θ , Φ profiles are practically small and presented in figure 18. At concentration level of $X_e = 61\%$ for the concentration driving force, $X_e - X_0$, has no effect on the concentration profile. Only in the extremely large driving force $X_e - X_0 = 40\%$ the change in the concentration profile can be noticeable. On the other hand, the driving force has significant effect on the transfer rates. This is presented by the enhancement factor, Ω , as defined in equation (3.64) and shown in Figure 23. For a sufficiently low concentration level the transfer rate is close to that obtained for infinite dilution, and thus $\Omega \rightarrow 1$. However, as the concentration level increases (for constant $(X_e - X_0)$, larger X_0) the enhancement factor exceeds 1.0, implying an enhanced transfer rate for finite dilution, both for the isothermal case ($\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 0$) and non-isothermal conditions ($\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} > 0$). As is indicated in Figure 6, the enhancement factor is higher for the isothermal case, particularly for a large driving force, while for $(X_e - X_0) \rightarrow 0$ the isothermal and non-isothermal solutions yield identical augmentation. Also to be noted, the increasing in the driving force (for instance at constant X_e) is identical to decreasing the inlet concentration level, X_0 , and approaching the conditions of infinite dilution, hence $\Omega \rightarrow 1.0$.

The increase in the transfer rate with increasing concentration level can be understood in view of equation (2.5), where both $(1-X_A)$ and the concentration gradient are included in the case of finite dilution. Inspection of Figures (8-10 and 14-17) indicates, in fact, that a deterioration of the concentration gradients at the transferring interface ($\zeta=0$) takes place as the absorbate concentration level increase. However, the transfer rate for finite dilution is determined by both the concentration gradient and the dilution term $(1 - X^*)$, as indicated by equation (3.52). The enhancement factor, Ω , represents the augmentation of the mass transfer coefficient due to the inclusion of the convective term in equation (2.4). Therefore, it is evident that when high absorbate concentration levels are considered, neglecting the convection term may lead to significantly under-predicted absorption rates.

As the solutions presented herein are limited to low penetration condition ($u \sim U_{max}$), it is of interest to check the down stream distance where this assumption is still valid. For instance with a parabolic velocity profile, the velocity at the near-interface region deviates only 10% from U_{max} for $y_{cr} = \frac{y_{1cr}}{\delta} = 1/3$. Based on the definitions of z and equations (3.11), a given y_{cr} corresponds to

$$x_{cr} = \frac{x_{1cr}}{\delta} \leq \frac{Pe_m}{4} \left[\frac{y_{cr}}{\zeta(\Phi = 0.01\Phi^*)} \right]^2 \quad (3.65)$$

Where -

$\zeta(\Phi = 0.01\Phi^*)$ - identifies the penetration of the diffusion boundary layer defined as that location where Φ has dropped to 1% of the interfacial value.

Figures 20 represents $\zeta(\Phi = 0.01\Phi^*)$ versus the concentration level.

Consistent with the trends already shown in Figure 8-10 and 14-17, increasing the absorbate concentration level results in an enhanced penetration of the diffusion boundary layer into the film. It should be kept in mind that the applicability of the solutions is physically limited to x as given by equation (3.65). For example, at a concentration level of $x^*=0.81$ Figure 20 yields $\zeta(\Phi=0.01\Phi^*)=4$, and thus equation (3.65) for $Pe_m \sim 10^6$ and y_{cr} yields $x_{cr} = \frac{x_{1cr}}{\delta} < 1700$, beyond which the validity of the low penetration assumption becomes weak. Clearly for $x^* \rightarrow 0$, $\zeta(\Phi=0.01\Phi^*) \rightarrow 1.78$ as obtained by the error function solution. Figures 20-21 describe the effect of the heat/mass coupling parameter. For lower values of this parameter the penetration is larger. This can be expected as for low values of heat/mass coupling parameter the mass transfer control hence larger penetration results due to the higher transfer rates associated with the higher concentration levels.

Finally, it is interesting to note the variation of the integration constant C_3 as obtained iteratively by equation (3.65) and shown in Figures 25-27. Having the constant C_3 all other constants C_1 , C_2 and C_4 are easily determined by equation (3.36)-(3.39). Thus, the evaluation of C_3 from Figures 25-27 may be helpful to estimate other calculated points not detailed in the previous Figures. As it is shown in figures 25-27 as the situation becomes less mass controlled the C_3 approaches zero consistent with the conclusions from Appendix B.

It has been shown that in physical systems where the absorbate concentration level is finite and is comparable to that of the absorbent component, as in hygroscopic condensation, the convective term in the lateral direction is to be accounted for. The inclusion of the

convective term is of importance as it results in enhanced transfer rates. Therefore, the use of empirical correlations, or models, obtained for an infinite absorbate dilution, may yield conservative transfer rates in the design of hygroscopic condensation evaporation systems.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

The major conclusions which evolve from the model developed in this study regarding isothermal and non isothermal absorption are summarized bellow.

- 1) The coupling between the heat and mass transfer is mainly due to the sensitivity of the equilibrium condition at the free interface to the interfacial temperature.
- 2) The coupling between the absorption and heat transfer phenomena is expressed by the parameter $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$. For small values of this parameter the coupling between the mass and heat transfer is rather small and the process may be considered as "mass transfer controlled". When the coupling parameter is increased the process gradually becomes "heat transfer controlled".
- 3) A model which is based on the assumption of infinitely diluted absorbate may lead to a significant error when attempting to describe absorption in a system with a finite concentration level. The increase in the concentration level affects a significant increase in the absorption rate. The boundary layer grows faster at higher concentration levels and therefore, the assumption of an infinitely thick film becomes weaker (relative to the case of infinite dilution).
- 4) For high values of the coupling parameter $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$ where the process becomes actually heat transfer controlled, the deviations caused by assuming an infinite absorbate dilution are reduced.
- 5) The effect of the nominal driving force for absorption, which can be expressed as the difference between the entry concentration and the equilibrium concentration, is rather small.
- 6) The influence of absorbate concentration level is apparent mainly for small z 's (close to the free interface, and/or farther downstream).
- 7) Although the predicted Nusselt numbers are unaffected by the absorbate concentration level and the process driving force, the heat transfer rates are dependent on both. When the concentration

level is increased the free interface is heated up due to the enhanced absorption, resulting in an increase of the thermal driving force results (compared to the case of infinite dilution).

In order to formulate the model, some assumptions were made, with constraints on the applicability of the model. For example, at high concentrations the absorption rate is very high, therefore the region where the assumption of uniform velocity is still reasonable may be limited to relatively short downstream distance (short contact time). Future possible research directions are suggested:

- 1) relaxing the assumption of low penetration and exploring the effect of concentration level in nonisothermal absorption over finite transferring surfaces with isothermal or adiabatic conditions at the solid wall,
- 2) investigating the change in the downstream flow rate resulting from the mass absorbed upstream (due to the higher absorption rate associated with high absorbate concentration it may be necessary also to check the coupling with the momentum equation),
- 3) exploring the effect of concentration level and process driving force in turbulent film flow,
- 4) extending the solutions for nonisothermal-absorption at different concentration levels for different geometries,
- 5) developing a model for nonisothermal absorption at high absorbate concentration level when the absorption process takes place at the near wall region (e.g. soluble wall).

5. Appendix A

This appendix deals with the solution to the ordinary differential equation (2.15) which was obtained in the process described in chapter 2 and chapter 3.

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{1}{E\Phi+1-\frac{C_0}{C}} \frac{d\Phi}{dz} \right] + 2z \frac{d\Phi}{dz} = 0 \quad (a.1)$$

Substituting $\beta = E\Phi+1-\frac{C_0}{C}$ into equation (a.1) the latter becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \frac{d\beta}{dz} \right] + 2z \frac{d\beta}{dz} = 0. \quad (a.2)$$

In this stage the equation (a.2) can be generalized to contain any positive continuous weight function of z . The reason for this generalization is that there might be cases where a different transformation or a different equation can yield a similar form of equation but with a different weight function. Also, sometimes different boundary conditions require a different similarity variable, which might yield a change in the weight function.

Moreover, one can find a partial differential equation which can be transferred into a similar form of ordinary differential equation but with a different weight function. So, a more general case is discussed.

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{1}{\beta'} \frac{d\beta'}{dz} \right] + f(z) \frac{d\beta'}{dz} = 0 \quad (a.3)$$

Equation (a.3) when multiplied by

$$\phi(z) = \exp \left[\int_0^z f(\xi) \beta'(\xi) d\xi \right], \quad (a.4)$$

where ξ is a dummy variable,
can be easily rearranged into

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{\phi(z)}{\beta'} \frac{d\beta'}{dz} \right] = 0. \quad (a.5)$$

Double integration of equation (a.5) yields:

$$\beta'(z) = \exp \left[C_3 \int_0^z \exp \left[-\int_0^\eta f(\xi) \beta'(\xi) d\xi \right] d\eta + C_4 \right]. \quad (a.6)$$

Equation (a.6) is a Volterra integral equation. It is well known from functional analysis that this type of equation may be solved by applying an iterative scheme, for any arbitrary initial guess of $\beta(\xi)$ (see Lovitt [L4]). After application of the iterative scheme one can obtain a "continuous integral". This "continuous integral" has a beginning but does not have an end. Since the solution does not depend on the initial guess, the end can be omitted. Practically, the iterative scheme turns out to be convergent for any $f(z) > 0$ where $z > 0$. Therefore, the solution is

$$\beta'(z) = \exp \left[\alpha_1'(z) \right] \quad (a.7)$$

$$\alpha_1'(z) = C_3 \int_0^z \exp \left[\alpha_2'(\xi) \right] d\xi + C_4 \quad (a.8)$$

$$\alpha_2'(\xi) = -\int_0^\xi f(\xi') \beta'(\xi') d\xi'.$$

Where -

$$\beta'(\xi') = \exp \left[\alpha_1'(\xi') \right] \quad (a.9)$$

To check if it is the solution, substitute into equation (a.3) recalling Leibneiz's rule.

$$\frac{d\beta'(z)}{dz} = \beta'(z) C_3 \exp(\alpha_2'(z)) \quad (a.10)$$

$$\frac{1}{\beta'(z)} \frac{d\beta'(z)}{dz} = C_3 \exp(\alpha_2'(z)) \quad (a.11)$$

Taking the derivative from the last result yields:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{1}{\beta'(z)} \frac{d\beta'(z)}{dz} \right] = -\beta'(z) C_3 f(z) \exp(\alpha_2'(z)) \quad (a.12)$$

It is easy to see that equation (a.3) is satisfied. For present case $f(z)$

is equal to $2z$ and the solution is:

$$\beta(z) = \exp \left[\alpha_1(z) \right] \quad (\text{a.13})$$

$$\alpha_1(z) = C_3 \int_0^z \exp \left[\alpha_2(\xi) \right] d\xi + C_4 \quad (\text{a.14})$$

$$\alpha_2(\xi) = - \int_0^\xi 2\xi' \beta(\xi') d\xi'$$

Where -

$$\beta(\xi') = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\xi') \right] \quad (\text{a.15})$$

6. Appendix B

It is interesting to show that the solution (the "continuous integral") to equation (2.14) approaches Higbie's solution. Higbie's solution is a solution to the governing equation which is obtained when low concentration is assumed. The governing equation in the present case is obtained by relaxing the assumption of low concentration. So, the solution of this equation should yield the same results as Higbie's solution when the concentration approaches zero.

One of the conclusions of the second and the third chapters is that C_3 approaches zero as concentration level decreases. It is described in figures 7, and 25-27. As well, for large values of the dimensionless normalized specific heat, $\frac{\Lambda}{\sqrt{Le}}$, the phenomenon is mostly governed by the heat transfer phenomenon. Hence, the process becomes more linear and C_3 obtains value which approach zero, as described in figure 29. Examination of equation (a.2), the solution, shows that it can be perturbed for small C_3 .

$$\beta(z) = \exp \left[\alpha_1(z) \right] \quad (b.1)$$

$$\alpha_1(z) = C_3 \int_0^z \exp \left[\alpha_2(\xi) \right] d\xi + C_4 \quad (b.2)$$

$$\alpha_2(\xi) = - \int_0^\xi 2\xi' \beta(\xi') d\xi'. \quad (b.3)$$

Where -

$$\beta(\xi') = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\xi') \right] \quad (b.4)$$

As a first approximation for small C_3 it can be assumed that

$$\beta(\xi') = \exp \left[\alpha_1(\xi') \right] = C_5 \left[1 + C_3 \text{INT}(\xi') \right]. \quad (b.5)$$

where -

$$C_5 = \exp(C_4)$$

$$\text{INT} = \int_0^{\xi} \exp \left[\alpha_2(\xi') \right] d\xi'$$

Now, substituting equation (b.5) into equation (b.3) yields

$$\alpha_2(\xi) = -\int_0^{\xi} 2\xi' \beta(\xi') d\xi' = -\int_0^{\xi} 2\xi' C_5 \left[1 + C_3 \text{INT} \right] d\xi' = -C_5 \left[\xi^2 + C_3 \text{INT}' \right] \quad (\text{b.6})$$

where -

$$\text{INT}' = \int_0^{\xi} 2\xi' \text{INT}(\xi') d\xi'$$

$$\beta(z) = C_5 \left[1 + C_3 \text{erf}(C_5 z) \right] \quad (\text{b.7})$$

From equation (2.22) for low concentration C_4 is ~ 0 thus

$$\beta(z) = 1 + C_3 \text{erf}(z). \quad (\text{b.8})$$

7. Computer programs

7.1 Program for chapter 2

This program is for the isothermal case

```
double precision phi(101), alfa1(101), alfa2(101), int(101)
double precision beta(101), betal(101), C, Co, Cstar, C3, C31, C4
double precision E, E1, E2, PI, delta, CCClog, z1, z2
open(8, file='out1', status='new', access='sequential')
```

```
C ***** INPUT OF INFORMATION *****
```

```
      Cstar=0.021
      Co=Cstar-0.02
      C=1.
      E1=1.0d-12
      E2=1.0d-12
      PI=3.141592654
      delta=.05
      lim=nint(5.0/delta)+1
do 10 i=1,lim
10  beta(i)=1.0
```

```
C ***** FIND first C3 *****
```

```
      E=(Co-Cstar)/C
      CCClog=dlog((C-Co)/(C-Cstar))
      C3=CCClog/(dsqrt(PI)/2.0)
      C4=dlog((C-Cstar)/C)
```

```
100  continue
      C31=C3
do 20 i=1,lim
20  betal(i)=beta(i)
```

```
C ***** FIND alfa2(i) *****
```

```
do 30 i=2,lim
      z1=(i-1)*delta*beta(i)
      z2=(i-2)*delta*beta(i-1)
30  alfa2(i)=alfa2(i-1)-2.0*Fint(z1, z2, delta)
```

```
C ***** DO integral against alfa2(i) *****
```

```
do 40 i=2,lim
40  int(i)=int(i-1)+Fint(dexp(alfa2(i)), dexp(alfa2(i-1)), delta)
```

```
C ***** FIND new C3 *****
  C3=CCCllog/int(lim)

C ***** FIND alfa1(i) and beta(i) *****
  do 50 i=1,lim
    alfa1(i)=C3*int(i)+C4
  50  beta(i)=dexp(alfa1(i))

C ***** CHECK the error *****
  if(dabs((C3-C31)/C31).ge.E2) goto 100
  do 60 i=2,lim
    if(dabs((beta(i)-beta1(i))/beta1(i)).ge.E1) goto 100
  60  continue

C ***** Final results *****
  do 70 i=1,lim
  70  phi(i)=(beta(i)-1+Co/C)/E

C ***** Print out *****
  write(8,200) C3,Cstar/C,Co/C
  write(8,300) (delta*(i-1),phi(i),i=1,lim)
200  format(3x,'C3 =',f10.7,6x,'Xstar =',f6.3,6x,'X =',f6.3,
  *          6x,'RemLe = .000'//7x,'z',10x,'Phi')
300  format(f9.2,f15.8)
  stop
  end

  function Fint(f1,f2,delta)
  double precision f1,f2,delta
  Fint=(f1+f2)*delta/2.0
  return
  end
```

7.2 Program for chapter 3

This program is for non-isothermal case

```
DOUBLE PRECISION phi(101), alfa1(101), alfa2(101), int(101)
DOUBLE PRECISION E1, E2, E3, C3, CC3, C31, C4, beta(101), betal(101)
DOUBLE PRECISION X, Xstar, X1, Xstar1, RemLe, PI, Pi2, delta
DOUBLE PRECISION C3min, C3max, z1, z2
open(8, file='out2', status='new', access='sequential')
```

C ***** INPUT OF INFORMATION *****

```
do 599 Xstar=0.02,0.71,0.2
    X=Xstar-0.01
    RemLe=0.2
    E1=1.0d-12
    E2=1.0d-12
    E3=1.0d-14
    PI=3.141592654
    delta=.05
    lim=nint(5.0/delta)+1
do 10 i=1,lim
10  beta(i)=1.0
```

C ***** FIND first C3 *****

```
X1=1.0-X
Xstar1=1.0-Xstar
Pi2=2.0/dsqrt(PI)
C3=dlog(X1/Xstar1)*Pi2
```

```
100 continue
C31=C3
C3max=1.0
C3min=0.0
do 20 i=1,lim
20  betal(i)=beta(i)
```

C ***** FIND alfa2(i) *****

```
do 30 i=2,lim
    z1=(i-1)*delta*beta(i)
    z2=(i-2)*delta*beta(i-1)
30  alfa2(i)=alfa2(i-1)-2.0*Fint(z1,z2,delta)
```

C ***** DO integral against alfa2(i) *****

```
do 40 i=2,lim
40  int(i)=int(i-1)+Fint(dexp(alfa2(i)),dexp(alfa2(i-1)),delta)

C ***** FIND new C3 and C4 *****
90  CC3=C3
    C3=0.5*(C3max+C3min)
    if((Xstar1+RemLe/Pi2*C3)*dexp(C3*int(lim)).ge.X1) then
    C3max=C3
    else
    C3min=C3
    end if
    write(*,*) 'C3 =',C3
    if(dabs((CC3-C3)/CC3).ge.E3) goto 90
    C4=dlog(Xstar1+RemLe*C3/Pi2)

C ***** FIND alfa1(i) and beta(i) *****
do 50 i=1,lim
    alfa1(i)=C3*int(i)+C4
50  beta(i)=dexp(alfa1(i))

C ***** CHECK the error *****
    if(dabs((C3-C31)/C31).ge.E2) goto 100
    do 60 i=2,lim
    if(dabs((beta(i)-beta1(i))/beta1(i)).ge.E1) goto 100
60  continue

C ***** Final results *****
do 70 i=1,lim
70  phi(i)=(beta(i)-1.0+X)/(X-Xstar)

C ***** Print out *****
    write(8,200) C3,Xstar,X,RemLe
    write(8,300) (delta*(i-1),phi(i),i=1,lim)
200  format(3x,'C3 =',f10.7,6x,'Xstar =',f6.3,6x,'X =',f6.3,
    *           6x,'RemLe =',f6.3//7x,'z',10x,'Phi')
300  format(f9.2,f15.8)
599  continue
    stop
    end

function Fint(f1,f2,delta)
double precision f1,f2,delta
Fint=(f1+f2)*delta/2.0
```

return
end

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CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 1
Effect of absorbate concentration level on the concentration profiles

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 2
Comparison between Arnold's model and the present model

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 3
Effect of the concentration driving force on the concentration profiles, at 50%

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 4
Effect of the concentration driving force on the concentration profiles at 80%

PENETRATION DISTANCE

Figure 5
Effect of concentration level on the penetration distance

ENHANCEMENT FACTOR

Figure 6
Enhancement factor due to lateral convective term

INTEGRATION CONSTANT

Figure 7
Effect of absorbate concentration level on the integration constant, C_3

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 8
Effect of absorbate concentration level on the concentration profiles, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 5$

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 9
Effect of absorbate concentration level on the concentration profiles, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 1$

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 10
Effect of absorbate concentration level on the concentration profiles, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 0.2$

TEMPERATURE PROFILE

Figure 11
Effect of absorbate concentration on the temperature profiles, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 5$

TEMPERATURE PROFILE

Figure 12
Effect of absorbate concentration on the temperature profiles, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 1$

TEMPERATURE PROFILE

Figure 13
Effect of absorbate concentration on the temperature profiles, $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le} = 0.2$

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 14
Effect of heat/mass coupling parameter on the concentration profiles, $X_e = 21\%$

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 15
Effect of heat/mass coupling parameter on the concentration profiles, $X_e = 61\%$

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 16
Effect of heat/mass coupling parameter on the concentration profiles, $X_e = 81\%$

INTERFACIAL CONCENTRATION

Figure 17

Effect of concentration level and coupling parameter on the interfacial concentration

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 18
Effect of concentration driving force on the concentration profiles at 61%

CONCENTRATION PROFILE

Figure 19
Effect of concentration driving force on the concentration profiles at 81%

PENETRATION DISTANCE

Figure 20
Effect of coupling parameter on penetration distance

PENETRATION DISTANCE

Figure 21
Effect of absorbate concentration level on penetration distance

ENHANCEMENT FACTOR

Figure 22
Effect of absorbate concentration level on enhancement factor

ENHANCEMENT FACTOR

Figure 23
Effect of concentration driving force on the enhancement factor

ENHANCEMENT FACTOR

Figure 24
Effect of coupling parameter on the enhancement factor

INTEGRATION CONSTANT

Figure 25
Effect of absorbate concentraion on the intergration constant, C_3

INTEGRATION CONSTANT

Figure 26
Effect of coupling parameter on the integration constant, C_3

INTEGRATION CONSTANT

Figure 27
Effect of the concentration driving force on the integration constant, C_3

מבוא

תהליך ספיגת גז ע"י נוזל הוא תהליך בעל ישומים טכנולוגיים רבים. התחומים אשר בהם מופיע תהליך זה הם: מחליפי חום ו/או חומר במגע ישיר, תהליכים המתבצעים בראקטורים כימיים בתעשייה, הפרדת גזים מנוזל בתהליכי זיקוק, מחזור כוח המבוסס על ספיגה ועיבוי [M3]. לאחרונה קיים עניין רב בספיגת אדים על גבי תמיסות מלח מרוכזות, עקב הפוטנציאל הגלום בהשבת חום הספיגה להפקת אנרגיה. קיימות מספר גאומטריות מוכרות של תהליכים אלו, אך הגאומטריה של תהליך ספיגת אד ע"י קרום נוזלי מעניינת במיוחד. ספיגה בפילמים מאפשרת השגת מקדמי מעבר גבוהים ומעבר חום סימולטני לתוך תווך סמוך (דרך הדופן), בניגוד לתהליכי הספיגה אשר מתבצעים בתרסיסים או בעמודי מילוי אשר הם בדרך כלל אדיאבטיים. אפשריות אלו להחלפת חום ולהשגת מקדמי מעבר גבוהים, בנוסף לאפשרות לשנות את הגאומטריה של הקרום, מגדילה את הגמישות של מתכנן לבקר ולשלוט בתהליך. בדרך כלל במערכות של גז-נוזל תהליך הספיגה מלווה במעבר חום. קיים צימוד בין תופעות מעבר החום ומעבר המסה הנובע בעיקר מההעובדות הבאות:

- (א) החומר העובר דיפוזיה נושא איתו את אנרגיה,
- (ב) שינויי הריכוז או הטמפרטורה עקב מעבר חום או מסה משנים את התכונות הפיסיקליות של הנוזל,
- (ג) תהליך הספיגה מלווה בשחרור חום (חום מהול ו/או חום כמוס של האדים המתעבים) המחמם את הקרום,
- (ד) השפעה על תנאי השפה - מצב שיווי המשקל בפן הביניים חלוי בטמפרטורה ובריכוז. ישנן סיבות נוספות לצימוד הנ"ל כגון *Termo diffusion effects*, תופעות של ראקציות כימיות, וכו'.

מעבר לבעיות הנובעות מצימוד הקיים בין תופעות מעבר חום ומעבר מסה, רוב תהליכי הספיגה נעשים כאשר הנוזל הוא ברמת ריכוז סופית, לאו דווקא נמוכה של החומר הניספג. מחזור אדים המבוסס על תהליך הספיגה [M3] כמו גם תהליכי מיצוי הם דוגמאות לתהליכים בהם רמת הריכוז על החומר הנספג הקרום גבוה יחסית. יש לציין שמעבר חומר ברמת ריכוז גבוהה שונה ממעבר חומר ברמת ריכוז נמוכה. מעבר להשפעת רמת הריכוז של החומר שנספג בקרום של התכונות הפיזיקליות של הקרום רמת הריכוז של החומר הנספג משפיע על אופי המשוואה ההשלטת.

מעבר סימולטני של חום וחומר לא קל לאנליזה מתמטית אך קיימים מספר מחקרים תאורטיים בנושא, (לדוגמא ראה Grossman [G2]) המניחים רמת ריכוז נמוכה של המרכיב הנספג. על השפעת רמת הריכוז של קצבי ספיגה איזותרמית ניתן ללמוד מתוך עבודתו של Arnold [A3] העוסקת בספיגה איזותרמית בהנחת שטף מולרי קבוע בתווך אין סופי סטגננטי. בשלב הזה אין בנמצא מחקרים תאורטיים של מעבר סימולטני של חום וחומר ברמות ריכוז גבוהות של החומר הניספג.

מטרת העבודה היא לבנות מודל עבור מעבר חום וחומר לתהליך ספיגה לפילם נופל ברמות ריכוז גבוהות של המרכיב הניספג. מודל כזה יוכל בעתיד לשמש בסיס למודלים מתוחכמים יותר ובגאומטריות שונות.

מספרים חסרי מימד

$(\sigma^3 g^2) / (\rho^3 \nu^4)$	Fi
$u / (gh)^{0.5}$	Fr
מספר לואיס D_{AB} / α או Pe_T / Pe_m	Le
מספר רינולדס	Re
מספר שמים	Sc
מספר פיקלה המסי	Pe_m
מספר פיקלה התרמי	Pe_T
$(C_A - C_0) / (C_e - C_0)$	Φ
חום עיבוי-ספיגה חסר המימד $(LeHa(C_e - C_0)) / (\rho C_p (T_e - T_0))$	Λ
$(T - T_0) / (T_e - T_0)$	Θ
היחס X_A / X^*	Ξ

אינדקס תחתון

חומר הניספג	A
חומר הסופג	B
גז המיתעבה	v
בבניסה	0
בשיווי משקל ללא שינוי בפרמטר השני	e
מקסימום	max

אינדקס עליון

בשיווי משקל	*
ממוצע	-
מיהול איך סופי	0

רשימת סימנים

<u>שם</u>	<u>סימן</u>
קבועי החומר התלויים בחומר ולחץ משוואה (3.10)	b,d
צפיפות המולרית של החומר $[mole/m^3]$	C
צפיפות המולרית של המרכיב הניספג $[mole/m^3]$	C_A
צפיפות המולרית בכניסה של המרכיב הניספג $[mole/m^3]$	C_0
החום הסגולי של הנוזל $[kJ/kg \cdot ^\circ C]$	C_p
צפיפות שיווי המישקל של המרכיב הניספג $[mole/m^3]$	C^*
מקדם המסה המולקולרי $[m^2/sec]$	D_{AB}
$(C_0 - C^*) / C$	E
קבוע הגרביטציה $[m/sec^2]$	g
גובה הפילם $[m]$	h
חום הספיגה $[kJ/kmol]$	Ha
מקדם מעבר החום של הנוזל $[kW/m \cdot ^\circ C]$	k
שטף המולרי של מרכיב A בכיוון x_1 $[mole/sec \cdot m^2]$	N_{Ax1}
שטף המולרי של מרכיב A בכיוון y_1 $[mole/sec \cdot m^2]$	N_{Ay1}
שטף המולרי של מרכיב B בכיוון x_1 $[mole/sec \cdot m^2]$	N_{Bx1}
שטף המולרי של מרכיב B בכיוון y_1 $[mole/sec \cdot m^2]$	N_{By1}
לחץ המקומי בנוזל $[Pa]$	P
הלחץ שיווי המשקל של המרכיב הניספג $[Pa]$	P_v
מהירות הנוזל $[m/sec]$	u
מהירות בכיוון הזרימה $[m/sec]$	U
מהירות בכיוון ניצב לזרימה $[m/sec]$	v
עובי האלמנט בכיוון ניצב ל y_1 ול x_1 $[m]$	W
מרחק במורד הזרם $[m]$	X_1
מרחק מנורמל במורד הזרם	x
היחס המולרי של המרכיב הניספג	X_A, X
מרחק בניצב לזרימה $[m]$	y_1
מרחק מנורמל בניצב לזרימה	y

אותיות יוניות

הדיפוזיות התרמית של הנוזל $[m^2/sec]$	α
הספיקה המסית של הנוזל $[kg/sec \cdot sec]$	Γ
עובי הפילם $[m]$	δ
זווית נטיה של משטח הזרימה	θ
צמיגות הנוזל $[kg/m \cdot sec]$	μ
צמיגות קינמטית $[m^2/sec]$	ν
צפיפות הנוזל $[kg/m^3]$	ρ
מתח פנים $[N/m]$	σ
מאמץ הגזירה על פני הנוזל $[Pa]$	τ_0

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88	השפעת כוח הדחף של הריכוז על פרופיל הריכוז ב 50%	3
89	השפעת כוח הדחף של הריכוז על פרופיל הריכוז ב 80%	4
90	השפעת רמת הריכוז על מרחק החדירה	5
91	תאור מקדם הגברה עקב אבר ההסעה	6
92	השפעת רמת הריכוז על קבוע האינטגרציה	7
93	השפעת רמת הריכוז על פרופיל הריכוז ב $5 = \Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$	8
94	השפעת רמת הריכוז על פרופיל הריכוז ב $1 = \Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$	9
95	השפעת רמת הריכוז על פרופיל הריכוז ב $0.2 = \Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$	10
96	השפעת רמת הריכוז על פרופיל הטמפרטורה ב $5 = \Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$	11
97	השפעת רמת הריכוז על פרופיל הטמפרטורה ב $1 = \Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$	12
98	השפעת רמת הריכוז על פרופיל הטמפרטורה ב $0.2 = \Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$	13
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תקציר

תהליכי ספיגת אדים לתמיסות נוזל, ולתמלחות במיוחד, מאופינים ברמת ריכוז גבוהה של מרכיב הנספג. כמעט כל המחקרים התאורטיים עד עכשיו הזניחו את השפעת רמת הריכוז של המרכיב הנספג על קצב ספיגת האדים. מטרת העבודה זו היא לחקור באופן אנליטי את השפעת רמת הריכוז של המרכיב הניספג בקרום הנוזל על תהליך הספיגה.

העבודה התאורטית היא הרחבה של תאוריית [G3] Highbie לספיגה איזותרמית, והרחבה של הפתרון של [G3] Grossman למקרה של ספיגה לא איזותרמית, שהניחו רמת ריכוז נמוכה של המרכיב ניספג בקרום וזמן מגע קצר.

האנליזה בוצעה בשני שלבים: תחילה פותח מודל עבור ספיגה איזותרמית ולאחר מכן פותח מודל עבור ספיגה לא איזותרמית, תוך התחשבות בתהליכי מעבר סימולטניים של חום וחומר. ההנחות החשובות יותר שנעשו לצורך פיתוח המודל הם: (א) זמן מגע קצר (ב) עובי הקרום אחיד (ג) התכונות הפיסיקליות של הקרום קבועות.

המשוואה השלטת על מעבר המסה היא משוואה לא ליניארית בריכוז המרכיב הניספג בניגוד למקרה של ריכוז נמוך שבו המשוואה ניתנת לקרוב ע"י משוואה ליניארית. במהלך העבודה נמצאה הצגה אנליטית של פתרון המשוואה השלטת על מעבר המסה. במקרה של ספיגה איזותרמית הפיתרון הוליך לשתי משוואות אלגבריות ואילו הפתרון במקרה של ספיגה לא איזותרמית הוביל לארבע משוואות אלגבריות. פתרון המערכות המשוואות האלגבריות בשני המקרים בוצע נומרית בעזרת מחשב.

אחת המסקנות החשובות הנובעת מהמחקר הנה, שתאוריות ספיגה המניחות ריכוז נמוך של המרכיב הניספג עלולות להביא להערכה מוטעת של קצבי הספיגה של אדים לתמלחות. יתר על כן, נמצא שקצב המעבר גדל עם גידול רמת הריכוז. נובע מכך, שקצב גידול שכבת הגבול מהיר יותר מאשר בפילם עם ריכוז נמוך.

הצימוד הקיים בין מעבר המסה והחום בספיגה לא איזותרמית (בה תהליך הספיגה מלווה בשחרור חום) גורם לירידה משמעותית בקצבי הספיגה. זאת, עקב רגישות ריכוז שיווי המשקל בפן הביניים לטמפרטורת הפן החופשי. מידת הצימוד הקימת בין תופעת הספיגה ומעבר החום באה לידי ביטוי בפרמטר $\Lambda/\sqrt{Le}$. ככל שהפרמטר גדול יותר כך גדלה מידת הצימוד בין תופעת הספיגה ומעבר החום. שטפי החום כשטפי המסה גדולים מאלו מאשר מתקבלים במקרה של מיהול אין סופי (הערה, למרות שמספרי נוסלדט נשארים זהים שטפי החום גדולים יותר כתוצאה מכוח דחף גדול יותר).

הכרת תודה

עבודה זו, שערכה כשש שנים ארבע מתוכם בארצות הברית, תחילה ניכתבה בעיברית ואחר כך באנגלית. מטבע הדברים שהיו לעבודה כזאת הרבה שותפים אשר אני רוצה להודות להם.

תודתי נתונה לפרופ' דויד מועלם - מרון ופרופ' נעימה בראונר על הדרכה, והעידוד שהושיטו לי במהלך העבודה.

ברצוני להביע את תודתי הכנה לגברת טליה בנטביץ אשר הקדישה לי זמן רב ועברה על כתב היד ותקנה את העברית הדלה שלי.

הוקרתי לפרופ' טוביה מילוא אשר היה לי מורה ואשר כבד אותי בלהיות אסיסטנט שלו בקורס "מכניקת זרימה מתקדמת". כמו כן אני רוצה להודות לו על העזרה וטורה שטרח לקראת נסיעתי לארצות הברית.

תודה לכל חברי במחלקה אשר עזרו לי בעצות מועילות בשעות הקשות. כן שלוחה, תודתי לכל אנשי סגל במחלקה בפרט, ובפקולטה בכלל אשר שסייעו בידי במהלך מחקר הזה, במיוחד לצוות הטכני.

אני רוצה להודות מקרב לב לחברי במינסוטה אשר עברו על עבודה שלי ותיקנו את השגיאות באנגלית.

ליהודית, תודה על כל האהבה אשר נתת לי במשך כל העבודה הזאת. את היית השראה עבורי. בלעדי החיבה שלך אני לא יודע אם הייתי מסוגל לעבור את התקופה הקשה זאת. אני רק מצטער שלא קיבלנו את מה שרצינו.

העבודה זו מוקדשת לזכרו
של

פרופ' מיכאל (מיכה) בנטביץ

מדען, אידאליסט, מורה, אדם והחבר
שניפטר בטרם עת בתאריך
8 למאי 1987

אוניברסיטת תל אביב

הפקולטה להנדסה

מחלקת לזרימה ומעבר חום

ספיגה היגרסקופית לקרום נוזלי:
השפעת רמת ריכוז התמלחת.

חיבור זה הוגש כעבודת גמר לקראת התואר "מוסמך אוניברסיטה"
בהנדסת באוניברסיטה תל אביב

על - ידי
ג'ניק מאירסון

העבודה הוכנה באוניברסיטת תל אביב במחלקת לזרימה ומעבר חום
בהדרכת פרופ' דויד מועלם מרון ופרופ' נעימה בראונר

טבת תשנ"ב